

Listing Minimal Vertex Cutsets in Ranked Order

Batya Kenig

Abstract

Let G be an undirected graph, and s, t distinguished vertices of G . A minimal st -separator is an inclusion-wise minimal vertex-set whose removal places s and t in distinct connected components. We consider the problem of listing the minimal st -separators of G in ascending order of their weight (or cardinality). We present such a ranked-enumeration algorithm parameterized by *branch-depth*, a parameter introduced by Telle and Villanger [42]. Our ranked enumeration algorithm has a delay of $\text{poly}(|V(G)|, |E(G)|)3^{\lceil \frac{4\ell}{3} \rceil}$, where ℓ is the branch-depth of G pertaining to the pair $\{s, t\}$, making it the first fixed-parameter-delay enumeration algorithm for this problem. In the process, we provide new characterizations of minimal st -separators that are of independent interest, and describe the obstacles for obtaining a polynomial delay algorithm.

1 Introduction

Consider a finite graph $G(V, E)$ with nodes $V = V(G)$ and edges $E = E(G)$. For two distinguished nodes $s, t \in V(G)$, an st -vertex-cut is a subset $S \subseteq V(G)$ such that s and t reside in distinct connected components of the graph that results from G by removing vertices S and their adjacent edges; an st -edge-cut is a subset $A \subseteq E(G)$ such that s and t reside in distinct connected components of the graph $G(V, E \setminus A)$. Vertex and edge cuts are widely studied in graph theory, with a long and deep history, that is motivated by a wide range of applications in computer science [36]. Finding an optimal (e.g., minimum weight) edge-cut and vertex-cut are fundamental problems, that are solved in polynomial time using network flow techniques [23, 16, 15]. A natural extension is the task of their enumeration, and in particular, enumerating edge and vertex-cuts in ranked order by their size or weight. A polynomial-delay algorithm for enumerating st -edge-cuts in ascending order of their weight was presented by Vazirani and Yannakakis [43], and before that, an algorithm for enumerating the best K st -edge-cuts was presented by Hamacher [21]. Both of these algorithms apply the known partitioning technique due to Lawler [32, 33, 19]. In this work, we focus on st -vertex-cuts, that in the literature are usually termed st -separators [2, 26, 39]. An st -separator $S \subseteq V(G)$ is a *minimal st -separator* if no strict subset of S is an st -separator. We say that S is a *minimum-cardinality st -separator* if $|S'| \geq |S|$ for every st -separator S' .

Fixed Parameter Tractable (FPT) algorithms [10, 17] are those with running time $O(n^c f(k))$, for a constant c independent of both the size of the input n , and the parameter k , and f is a computable function. The treewidth of a graph is an important graph complexity measure that occurs as a parameter in many FPT algorithms [17, 6] that operate over the *tree decomposition* of the graph. Therefore, much work has been invested in computing the treewidth and finding optimal tree decompositions, which are NP-complete problems [1]. In this setting, a central algorithm is the one due to Bouchitté and Todinca [7] (BT algorithm) for finding optimal tree decompositions in terms of both width and *fill-in*. The BT algorithm has been shown to be applicable to a range of cost functions [5, 18], and its implementations consistently occupy the top spots of the Parameterized Algorithms and Computational Experiments challenge (PACE) [12, 30]. In particular, recent work has adapted the BT algorithm to find tree decompositions that are optimal with respect to the

size of the factors associated with its nodes [30, 34], providing the best performance guarantee for probabilistic inference algorithms [28, 11].

The BT algorithm and its extensions employ a subroutine for listing the set of minimal separators of the graph [7]. Current state-of-the-art algorithms for finding an optimal tree-decomposition of an input graph, with respect to some cost function, require the set of minimal separators with bounded cost [40, 30, 29]. For example, a tree decomposition whose width is k can only represent minimal separators whose size is at most k [40]. As another example, we consider the setting of probabilistic inference [28, 11]. The complexity of probabilistic inference algorithms is dominated by the size of the largest factor (table) associated with any node in the tree decomposition; its size is a product of the domain-sizes of its members [28, 11]. In this setting, every variable is represented by a vertex whose weight is the size of its domain. The weight of a minimal separator is the sum of weights of its members [30]. Hence, every tree decomposition whose nodes have bounded costs can only represent minimal separators of bounded costs. Consequently, an algorithm that returns the minimal separators of the graph in ascending order of weight can lead to significant performance gains in finding optimal tree decompositions, since it can be aborted once separators of weight greater than some threshold are returned. Another parameter of interest is *treedepth* [45, 44], important in a variety of combinatorial optimization problems. Its computation also requires all the minimal separators of the graph that contain at most k vertices, for some bound k . Motivated by these tasks, we study the problem of enumerating the minimal *st*-separators of a graph in ranked order according to their weight.

Enumerating minimal separators in ascending order of cardinality or weight refines and extends two well-studied enumeration problems [29]: enumeration of all minimal separators, and enumeration of all (not necessarily minimal) separators of size at most k . Berry et al. [2] developed an efficient algorithm that lists the minimal separators of a graph with a delay of $O(|V(G)|^3)$ between consecutive outputs. This algorithm, as well as others [26, 39, 38], lists the minimal separators in arbitrary order. Kanevsky [24] developed a complicated algorithm that enumerates all the separators whose size is at most k , but his algorithm outputs non-minimal separators as well. Finally, a strict subset of the set of all minimal *st*-separators known as *important separators* [10, 35] posses a special structure that allows enumerating all important *st*-separators of size at most q , in polynomial delay [9].

Let $P = (u = v_1, \dots, v_{q-1}, v_q = v)$ be an induced *uv*-path in G . The *branch-depth* [42] of P is $b(P) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} |N_G[v_1, \dots, v_{q-1}]| - 1$; it is the size of the set containing $\{v_1, \dots, v_{q-1}\}$ and their neighbors minus 1 (see (1) in Section 2). We let ℓ denote the maximal branch-depth of any induced path with an endpoint in the set $\{s, t\}$. In general, $b(P) \leq n$, and there exists a family of graphs where this bound is tight [42]. Our ranked enumeration algorithm outputs the minimal *st*-separators of G in ascending order of weight. The delay between the output of consecutive minimal *st*-separators is $O(3^{\frac{4\ell}{3}} \cdot nT(n, m)K^2)$ where $n = |V(G)|$, $m = |E(G)|$, $T(n, m)$ is the time to find a single minimum-weight *st*-separator in a graph with n vertices and m edges, and K is the size of the largest minimal *st*-separator reported by the enumeration algorithm. Hence, the algorithm runs in FPT-delay with parameter ℓ .

To prove correctness, we prove new characterizations of minimal separators that are of independent interest, and reveal close ties between the problem of ranked enumeration of minimal separators and that of finding and enumerating disjoint connected subgraphs and paths [42, 25]. Finally, we apply a recent “buffering technique” [41] that converts an enumeration algorithm that outputs every solution at most a constant α number of times, to a distinct enumeration algorithm, at the price of increasing the delay by a factor of at most $\alpha \cdot n$. In the Appendix of this paper, we present a new, simplified algorithm for enumerating the *st*-separators (i.e., not necessarily minimal)

in ascending order of weight with polynomial-delay, and an algorithm that enumerates only the minimum st -separators of a graph in polynomial delay.

Challenges and Techniques. In any ranked enumeration algorithm, finding the top element is basically an *optimization problem*. In our case, there are well known algorithms for finding a *minimum-weight st -separator* [23, 16]. For $k > 1$, finding the k th ranking item amounts to computing the optimal minimal st -separator under the restriction that it is not among the first $k - 1$ items previously returned. Handling this constraint is the main challenge when designing ranked enumeration and top- K algorithms.

The technique of Lawler and Murty [33] provides a general framework for ranked enumeration corresponding to discrete optimization problems. The main idea is to reduce a ranked enumeration problem to an optimization problem with constraints [19]. In the standard approach to applying the Lawler-Murty technique, the algorithm first finds the optimal solution S (e.g., minimum-weight st -separator), then the subspace of solutions (excluding S) is partitioned using *inclusion* and *exclusion* constraints. The straightforward approach to applying the Lawler-Murty method to ranked enumeration of minimal st -separators is by solving the following optimization problem: find the minimum-weight minimal st -separator that excludes a subset of vertices $U \subseteq V(G)$ and includes a subset $I \subseteq V(G)$ of vertices, where $U \cap I = \emptyset$. Using this approach, we immediately hit an obstacle. In Appendix A, we show that deciding whether there exists a minimal st -separator that includes a distinguished vertex $v \in V(G)$, is NP-complete by reduction from the 3-in-a-path problem [13]. Hence, we devise a different approach.¹

We define the constraints to represent sets of vertices that appear in the same or in distinct connected components. Let S be a minimum st -separator of G . We partition the set of remaining minimal st -separators into two disjoint sets: minimal st -separators that are *parallel* to S , and those that *cross* S . The notions of crossing and parallel minimal separators were introduced by Parra and Scheffler [37], and are formally defined in Section 2. We say that a minimal st -separator T is parallel to S if, in the graph that results by removing the vertices T (and their adjacent edges), there exists a single connected component containing vertices from S . Otherwise, we say that T *crosses* S .

Let ℓ be the maximal branch-depth of any induced path in G with an endpoint in $\{s, t\}$. Define $f(\ell) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} 3^{\lceil \frac{2\ell}{3} \rceil}$, and let K denote the size of the largest minimal st -separator printed by the algorithm. Given a minimum st -separator S , our ranked enumeration algorithm generates at most $K^2 f(\ell)$ graphs G^1, \dots, G^q such that a subset of vertices $T \subseteq V(G)$ is a minimal st -separator of G that crosses S if and only if T is a minimal st -separator of some G^i . A minimal st -separator that crosses S is a minimal st -separator in at most $f(\ell)$ of the graphs G^1, \dots, G^q . By applying the buffering technique [41], we obtain a delay of $O(nK^2 T(n, m) (f(\ell))^2)$. Proving that the set of graphs G^1, \dots, G^q have the properties described above relies on a new characterization of crossing minimal st -separators (Section 3) that is of independent interest. To generate the set of graphs G^1, \dots, G^q we apply an algorithm for enumerating induced paths by Telle and Villanger [42] that runs in time $O(n3^{\frac{\ell}{3}})$.

To handle minimal st -separators that are parallel to S , the algorithm generates two graphs H_1, H_2 such that T is a minimal st -separator of H_1 or H_2 if and only if T is a minimal st -separator of G that is parallel to S . In this case, S itself is the unique minimal st -separator common to both H_1 and H_2 , and by the construction of H_1 (and H_2), S is the unique minimal st -separator that is included in the neighborhood of s (neighborhood of t). Hence, we develop a simple way to avoid

¹Enumerating and optimizing over minimal st -separators that exclude a subset of vertices is tractable, and presented in Appendix D.

listing S . Since every minimal separator either crosses S or is parallel to S , then this covers all minimal st -separators distinct from S .

In Appendix D, we provide simple and efficient characterizations of vertices that are excluded from minimal st -separators, and of vertices included in a minimum st -separator. We then use these to present simple, polynomial-delay enumeration algorithms for listing all st -separators in ascending order based on cardinality or weight, and for listing only the minimum st -separators.

Organization. Following preliminaries and notation in Section 2, we prove a new characterization of crossing minimal st -separators in Section 3 that is essential to the ranked enumeration algorithm. In Section 4 we apply this characterization for generating a set of graphs that, together, contain precisely the set of minimal st -separators that cross a certain minimal st -separator S . In Section 5 we do the same for parallel minimal st -separators. Due to space constraints, the pseudocode that combines the results of Sections 4 and 5 into the ranked enumeration algorithm is deferred to Appendix B. Finally, in Appendix D we present simple, polynomial-delay enumeration algorithms for listing all (i.e., not necessarily minimal) st -separators in ascending order based on cardinality or weight, and for listing only the minimum-cardinality st -separators.

2 Preliminaries and Notation

Let G be an undirected graph with nodes $\mathbf{V}(G)$ and edges $\mathbf{E}(G)$, where $n = |\mathbf{V}(G)|$, and $m = |\mathbf{E}(G)|$. Let $v \in V$. We denote by $N_G(v) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{u \in \mathbf{V}(G) : (u, v) \in \mathbf{E}(G)\}$ the neighborhood of v , and by $N_G[v] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} N_G(v) \cup \{v\}$ the *closed* neighborhood of v . The degree of G is $d \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \max_{v \in \mathbf{V}(G)} N_G(v)$. For a subset of vertices $T \subseteq \mathbf{V}(G)$, we denote by $N_G(T) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \bigcup_{v \in T} N_G(v)$, and $N_G[T] \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} N_G(T) \cup T$. When the graph G is clear from the context we drop the subscript G . We denote by $G[T]$ the subgraph of G induced by T . Formally, $\mathbf{V}(G[T]) = T$, and $\mathbf{E}(G[T]) = \{(u, v) \in \mathbf{E}(G) : \{u, v\} \subseteq T\}$. If G' is a graph where $\mathbf{V}(G') = \mathbf{V}(G)$ and $\mathbf{E}(G) \subseteq \mathbf{E}(G')$, we say that G is a *subgraph* of G' , and G' is a *supergraph* of G .

Let $u, v \in \mathbf{V}(G)$. A *simple path* between u and v , also called a uv -path, is a finite sequence of distinct vertices $u = v_1, \dots, v_k = v$ where, for all $i \in [1, k - 1]$, $(v_i, v_{i+1}) \in \mathbf{E}(G)$, and whose two ends are u and v . A uv -path $u = v_1, \dots, v_k = v$ is *chordless* or *induced*, if $(v_i, v_j) \notin \mathbf{E}(G)$ whenever $|i - j| > 1$. G contains a P_k if it contains an induced path of length at least k ; otherwise it is P_k -free. Let $P = (v_1, \dots, v_k)$ be an induced path in G . The *branch-depth* [42] of P is:

$$b(P) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} |N_G[\{v_1, \dots, v_{k-1}\}]| - 1 \tag{1}$$

We let ℓ denote the maximal branch-depth among all induced path in G having an endpoint in $\{s, t\}$. That is, $\ell = \max\{\ell_s, \ell_t\}$ where $\ell_s = \max_{u \in \mathbf{V}(G)} \max_{P \in \mathcal{P}_{su}} b(P)$ where \mathcal{P}_{su} is the set of induced su -paths in G . Likewise, $\ell_t = \max_{u \in \mathbf{V}(G)} \max_{P \in \mathcal{P}_{ut}} b(P)$. It is an easy observation that if G is P_k -free with maximal degree d , then $\ell \leq kd$.

Two uv -paths are *internally disjoint* if there is no vertex that is an internal vertex for both paths. We say that a set of paths P_1, \dots, P_k for some $k \geq 1$, are *mutually induced paths* of G if each P_i is an induced path, the P_i s are pairwise vertex-disjoint, and there is no edge between vertices from different paths P_i and P_j [25].

A subset of vertices $V' \subseteq \mathbf{V}(G)$ is called a *connected component* of G if $G[V']$ contains a path between every pair of vertices in V' . Let V_1, V_2 denote two disjoint vertex subsets of $\mathbf{V}(G)$. We say that V_1 and V_2 are adjacent if there is at least one pair of adjacent vertices $v_1 \in V_1$ and $v_2 \in V_2$. We say that there is a path between V_1 and V_2 if there exist vertices $v_1 \in V_1$ and $v_2 \in V_2$ such that there is a path between v_1 and v_2 .

Let $T \subseteq \mathbf{V}(G)$ be a subset of vertices of graph G , and let $t \in T$. By *merging* T into vertex t , we refer to the operation that deletes all vertices in $T \setminus \{t\}$ from G , and adds an edge between t and every vertex in $N_G(T)$.

2.1 Minimal Separators

Let $s, t \in \mathbf{V}(G)$. For $X \subseteq \mathbf{V}(G)$, we let $\mathcal{C}_G(X)$ denote the set of connected components of $G[\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus X]$. The vertex set X is called a *separator* of G if $|\mathcal{C}_G(X)| \geq 2$, an *st-separator* if s and t are in different connected components of $\mathcal{C}_G(X)$, and a *minimal st-separator* if no proper subset of X is an *st-separator* of G . For an *st-separator* X , we denote by $C_s(G, X)$ and $C_t(G, X)$ the connected components of $\mathcal{C}_G(X)$ containing s and t respectively. When G and X are clear from the context, we denote these components by C_s and C_t respectively. The following is well-known.

Lemma 2.1. ([2]) A subset $X \subseteq \mathbf{V}(G)$ is a minimal *st-separator* if and only if there are two connected components $C_s \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} C_s(G, X), C_t \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} C_t(G, X) \in \mathcal{C}_G(X)$, such that $s \in C_s, t \in C_t$, and $N_G(C_s) = N_G(C_t) = X$; C_s and C_t are called *full components* of $\mathcal{C}_G(X)$.

A subset $X \subseteq \mathbf{V}(G)$ is a *minimal separator* if there exist a pair of vertices $u, v \in \mathbf{V}(G)$ such that X is a minimal *uv-separator*; it is a *clique minimal separator* if $G[X]$ is a clique. We denote by $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$ the minimal *st-separators* in G , and by $\mathcal{S}(G)$ the set of minimal separators of G .

Let $S, T \in \mathcal{S}(G)$ be two minimal separators of G . We say that S *crosses* T if there are vertices u and v in T , such that S is a *uv-separator*. Crossing is known to be a symmetric relation: S crosses T if and only if T crosses S [37]. Hence, if S crosses T , we say that S and T are *crossing*, and denote this relationship by $S \# T$ [37]. It follows from this definition, and the fact that crossing is a symmetric relationship, that if $S \# T$ then there exist two connected components $C_1, C_2 \in \mathcal{C}_G(S)$ such that $C_1 \cap T \neq \emptyset$, and $C_2 \cap T \neq \emptyset$. When S and T are non-crossing, then we say that they are *parallel*. It immediately follows that if S and T are parallel (non-crossing) then $S \subseteq C_S \cup T$ for some connected component $C_S \in \mathcal{C}_G(T)$ and $T \subseteq C_T \cup S$ for some $C_T \in \mathcal{C}_G(S)$. We denote by $S \parallel T$ the fact that S and T are parallel minimal separators.

Let $w : \mathbf{V}(G) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$ be a vertex weight function; for a subset $S \subseteq \mathbf{V}(G)$, we denote by $w(S) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \sum_{u \in S} w(u)$. A subset $S \subseteq \mathbf{V}(G)$ is a *minimum-weight st-separator* in G if $w(S') \geq w(S)$ for every other *st-separator* S' . We denote by $\kappa_{st}(G)$ the weight of a minimum-weight *st-separator* of G , and by $\mathcal{L}_{st}(G)$ the set of all minimum-weight *st-separators* of G . When $w(u) = 1$ for all $u \in \mathbf{V}(G)$, then $\kappa_{st}(G)$ is the connectivity of G , and $\mathcal{L}_{st}(G)$ the set of minimum *st-separators* of G . There is an algorithm, based on network-flow techniques, that finds a minimum-weight *st-separator* in polynomial time.

Theorem 2.1. (Theorem 2.4 in [23]) Let G be an undirected graph with non-negative vertex weights defined by $w : \mathbf{V}(G) \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^+$. There is an algorithm that finds the minimum weight vertex-separator in time $O(\kappa_1 nm \log(\frac{n^2}{m}))$, where $\kappa_1 \leq \frac{m}{n}$ is the unweighted vertex connectivity. The space is $O(m)$.

In the following we denote by $T(n, m)$ the time to find a minimum-weight *st-separator* using the algorithm of [23]. Since we can limit ourselves to considering the connected component of G containing s and t , then we can assume that $m \geq n - 1$, and hence that $T(n, m) \leq m^2 \log n$.

2.2 The Induced Disjoint Paths Problem and Minimal AB -separators

Let A and B be two disjoint, non-adjacent subsets of $\mathbf{V}(G)$. A vertex set X is called an *AB-separator* if there are two distinct, connected components $C_A, C_B \in \mathcal{C}_G(X)$, where $A \subseteq C_A$ and $B \subseteq C_B$, and

a *minimal AB-separator* if no proper subset of X is an AB -separator. We denote by $\mathcal{S}_{AB}(G)$ the set of minimal AB -separators in G .

Definition 2.1. ([25]) [Induced Disjoint Paths Problem] Let G be a graph, and $\{(s_1, t_1), \dots, (s_k, t_k)\}$ a collection of vertex pairs where, for all $i \in [1, k]$, $s_i \neq t_i$, and $\{s_i, t_i\} \cap \{s_j, t_j\} = \emptyset$ for all $i \neq j$. The problem is to decide whether G has a set of k mutually induced paths P_1, \dots, P_k such that P_i is an (s_i, t_i) path for $i \in [1, k]$.

Theorem 2.2. ([25]) The Induced Disjoint Paths Problem is NP-hard when $k = 2$ and G is a general undirected graph.

Theorem 2.3. Let A and B be two disjoint, non-adjacent subsets of $V(G)$. Deciding whether $\mathcal{S}_{AB}(G) \neq \emptyset$ is NP-hard.

Proof. Consider an instance of the induced disjoint path problem where $k = 2$, and let $\{(s_1, t_1), (s_2, t_2)\}$ be the pair of disjoint, non-adjacent vertex-pairs. Define $A = \{s_1, t_1\}$ and $B = \{s_2, t_2\}$. Then $\mathcal{S}_{AB}(G) \neq \emptyset$ if and only if there exist two non-adjacent, disjoint, connected components $Z_A \supseteq A$ and $Z_B \supseteq B$. But this is if and only if there exist two mutually induced paths P_1 and P_2 between s_1 and t_1 and s_2 and t_2 , respectively (i.e., P_1 and P_2 are non-adjacent and vertex-disjoint). \square

Theorem 2.3 implies that finding (and hence enumerating) minimal AB -separators in the general case is intractable. As stated below, the state of affairs is different when $G[A]$ and $G[B]$ are connected; proof is deferred to Appendix C.

Theorem 2.4. Let A and B be two disjoint, non-adjacent subsets of $V(G)$. Let G' denote the graph that results by merging A and B into vertices a and b respectively. If $G[A]$ and $G[B]$ are connected, then $\mathcal{S}_{AB}(G) = \mathcal{S}_{ab}(G')$.

The following Lemma and Corollary are important to our ranked enumeration algorithm.

Lemma 2.2. ([42]) Let $u, v \in V(G)$ be non-adjacent, and let $t \geq 0$ be an integer. There exist at most $3^{\frac{t}{3}}$ induced paths $P = (u = v_1, \dots, v_q, v_{q+1} = v)$ such that $b(P) \leq t$ (see (1)), and all these paths can be enumerated in $O(n3^{\frac{t}{3}})$ time.

Corollary 2.1. Let G be a P_k -free graph with maximal degree d , and let $u, v \in V(G)$ be non-adjacent vertices. There exist at most $3^{\frac{kd}{3}}$ induced paths $P = (u = v_1, \dots, v_q, v_{q+1} = v)$, and all these paths can be enumerated in $O^*(3^{\frac{kd}{3}})$ time.

Proof. Since G is P_k -free then $q \leq k - 1$ for every induced uv -path P . Every vertex on the induced path has at most d neighbors. Therefore $b(P) \leq (k - 1)d < kd$. The result immediately follows from Lemma 2.2. \square

2.3 Duplicate-Elimination with the Buffering Technique [41]

The buffering technique is a method of delaying the output of the results for the purpose of regularizing the delay. Consider an algorithm \mathcal{A} that enumerates the items in a set D with delay δ , but \mathcal{A} may output the same item $e \in D$ at most $\alpha - 1$ times, for some constant $\alpha \geq 2$, independent of the input. Then \mathcal{A} can be converted to an enumeration algorithm that lists distinct elements with a delay of $O(\alpha\delta \log |D|)$. The idea is to let \mathcal{A} generate α items (that are perhaps duplicates), between the output of the solutions, and works as follows. As \mathcal{A} runs, we use a priority queue B to store the set of distinct solutions that have been found by \mathcal{A} , but not yet printed, and a data

structure C to store the solutions already printed by \mathcal{A} . Each time \mathcal{A} generates a solution $e \in D$, we check whether $e \in B \cup C$ (this takes $O(\log |D|)$ time using standard data structures), in which case it is ignored; otherwise, we add e to B . After \mathcal{A} generates α items (this takes time $O(\alpha\delta)$), we output the top element in B , and transfer it to C . Finally, after \mathcal{A} has terminated, we output the remaining elements from B .

Suppose that \mathcal{A} has generated $t \cdot \alpha$ items for some $t \geq 1$, which may not be distinct. Since each element is generated at most $\alpha - 1$ times, then among the $t \cdot \alpha$ items generated, at least t are distinct. Since the algorithm prints a single item from B for every α items generated by \mathcal{A} , then after generating $t \cdot \alpha$ items, only $t - 1$ have been printed. Therefore, B must contain at least one non-seen element after generating $t \cdot \alpha$ items. This leads to a delay of $O(\alpha\delta \log |D|)$.

3 A Refined Characterization of Crossing Minimal st -separators

In this section, we prove a characterization of crossing minimal st -separators that will be instrumental in the partitioning phase of the ranked enumeration algorithm.

Proposition 3.1. Let $u, v \in \mathbf{V}(G) \setminus \{s, t\}$, and let $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$. Exactly one of the following holds:

1. $u \in C_s(G, T)$ and $v \in C_t(G, T)$.
2. $v \in C_s(G, T)$ and $u \in C_t(G, T)$.
3. There is a connected component $C \in \mathcal{C}_G(T)$, such that $\{u, v\} \subseteq T \cup C$.
4. There exist two distinct connected components $C_1, C_2 \in \mathcal{C}_G(T)$ where $\{C_1, C_2\} \neq \{C_s(G, T), C_t(G, T)\}$ such that $u \in C_1$ and $v \in C_2$.

Accordingly, we denote by:

$$\mathcal{S}_1^G(u, v) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G) : u \in C_s(G, T), v \in C_t(G, T)\} \quad (2)$$

$$\mathcal{S}_2^G(u, v) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G) : u \in C_t(G, T), v \in C_s(G, T)\} \quad (3)$$

$$\mathcal{S}_3^G(u, v) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G) : \exists C \in \mathcal{C}_G(T) : \{u, v\} \subseteq C \cup T\} \quad (4)$$

$$\mathcal{S}_4^G(u, v) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G) : \exists C_u, C_v \in \mathcal{C}_G(T), C_u \neq C_v, \\ \{C_u, C_v\} \neq \{C_s(G, T), C_t(G, T)\}, u \in C_u, v \in C_v\} \quad (5)$$

It is an easy observation that for every $u, v \in \mathbf{V}(G) \setminus \{s, t\}$:

$$\mathcal{S}_{st}(G) = \mathcal{S}_1^G(u, v) \cup \mathcal{S}_2^G(u, v) \cup \mathcal{S}_3^G(u, v) \cup \mathcal{S}_4^G(u, v) \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{S}_i^G(u, v) \cap \mathcal{S}_j^G(u, v) = \emptyset \text{ for } i \neq j \quad (6)$$

When the graph G is clear from the context, we write $\mathcal{S}_i(u, v)$ for $i \in [1, 4]$.

Theorem 3.1. Let $S, T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$. Then $S \# T$ if and only if there are two vertices $a, b \in S$ such that $a \in C_s(G, T)$ and $b \in C_t(G, T)$.

Proof. If $a \in C_s(G, T)$ and $b \in C_t(G, T)$, then by definition $S \# T$.

Now, suppose that $S \# T$. Then, by definition, $T \not\subseteq C_s(G, S) \cup S$. Let $w \in T \setminus (C_s(G, S) \cup S)$. We look at the induced graph $G[\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus (T - \{w\})]$. Since $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$, then every st -path in $G[\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus (T - \{w\})]$ passes through the vertex w , and there is at least one such st -path, that we call P_w . Since $\mathbf{V}(P_w) \cap (T - \{w\}) = \emptyset$, then it must hold that $\mathbf{V}(P_w) \subseteq C_s(G, T) \cup T \cup C_t(G, T)$. In other words, $P_w = P_1 - w - P_2$ where P_1 is the subpath of P_w from s to w (not including w), and P_2 is the subpath of P_w from w to t (not including w). In particular, $\mathbf{V}(P_1) \subseteq C_s(G, T)$ and $\mathbf{V}(P_2) \subseteq C_t(G, T)$. See Figure 1 for illustration.

Since $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$, then P_w must meet a vertex in S . That is, $\mathbf{V}(P_w) \cap S \neq \emptyset$. Let $a \in \mathbf{V}(P_w) \cap S$ be the vertex in S that is closest to s on the path P_w . We denote by P_a the subpath from s to a (without the endpoint a) on P_w . Since a is the first vertex on P_w that belongs to S , then $\mathbf{V}(P_a) \subseteq C_s(G, S)$. If $a \in \mathbf{V}(P_2)$, then w appears before a on the path P_w , which means that w is on the subpath P_a . In other words, if $a \in \mathbf{V}(P_2)$, then $w \in \mathbf{V}(P_a) \subseteq C_s(G, S)$. But this is a contradiction to the fact that $w \in T \setminus (C_s(G, S) \cup S)$. If $a = w$, we again arrive at a contradiction that $w \in T \setminus (C_s(G, S) \cup S)$. Therefore, it must hold that $a \in \mathbf{V}(P_1) \subseteq C_s(G, T)$.

We show that there exists a vertex $b \in S$ such that $b \in C_t(G, T)$ in the same way. Assuming $T \not\subseteq C_t(G, S) \cup S$, we let $w \in T \setminus (C_t(G, S) \cup S)$, and again look at the graph $G[\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus (T - \{w\})]$, and consider the st -path P_w through w in $G[\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus (T - \{w\})]$. Since the proof is the same as showing that $a \in C_s(G, T)$ above, we omit the rest. \square

Figure 1: Illustration for the proof of Theorem 3.1: the path P_w .

Theorem 3.2. Let $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$, and let $\{(u_1, v_1), \dots, (u_k, v_k)\}$ be a fixed order of the set of non-edges of $G[S]$ (i.e., $(u_i, v_i) \notin \mathbf{E}(G)$). For brevity, we denote by $\mathcal{S}_{34}(u_i, v_i) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathcal{S}_3(u_i, v_i) \cup \mathcal{S}_4(u_i, v_i)$. Then:

$$\{T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G) : T \not\# S\} = \bigsqcup_{i=1}^k \left(\mathcal{S}_1(u_i, v_i) \cap \bigcap_{j=1}^{i-1} \mathcal{S}_{34}(u_j, v_j) \right) \uplus \bigsqcup_{i=1}^k \left(\mathcal{S}_2(u_i, v_i) \cap \bigcap_{j=1}^{i-1} \mathcal{S}_{34}(u_j, v_j) \right) \quad (7)$$

where \uplus is the symbol for disjoint union.

Proof. We first note that for every pair $u, v \in \mathbf{V}(G)$ it holds that $\mathcal{S}_1(u, v) \cap \mathcal{S}_2(u, v) = \emptyset$, and $(\mathcal{S}_1(u, v) \cup \mathcal{S}_2(u, v)) \cap \mathcal{S}_{34}(u, v) = \emptyset$. Therefore, the union in (7) is disjoint.

Let $T \subseteq \mathbf{V}(G)$ be a set that belongs to the RHS of (7). By definition, $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$, and there exists a pair of non-adjacent vertices $u_i, v_i \in S$ where $T \in \mathcal{S}_1(u_i, v_i) \cup \mathcal{S}_2(u_i, v_i)$. That is, u_i and v_i reside in distinct connected components of $G[\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus T]$. Therefore, $T \in \{T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G) : T \not\# S\}$.

Now, let $T \in \{T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G) : T \not\# S\}$. By Theorem 3.1, there is a pair of non-adjacent vertices $u, v \in S$ where $u \in C_s(G, T)$ and $v \in C_t(G, T)$, or $u \in C_t(G, T)$ and $v \in C_s(G, T)$. Let (u_i, v_i) be the pair with the smallest index for which this condition holds. By definition, this means that $T \in \mathcal{S}_1(u_i, v_i) \cup \mathcal{S}_2(u_i, v_i)$, and that for every $j < i$ it holds that $T \in \mathcal{S}_{34}(u_j, v_j)$. That is, $T \in (\mathcal{S}_1(u_i, v_i) \cup \mathcal{S}_2(u_i, v_i)) \cap \bigcap_{j=1}^{i-1} \mathcal{S}_{34}(u_j, v_j)$. This completes the proof. \square

4 Characterizing Crossing Minimal st -separators Using Graphs

Let $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$. To apply Theorem 3.2 for the task of ranked enumeration of all minimal st -separators that cross S , we describe a set of graphs that partition the set $\{T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G) : T \not\# S\}$ as in Theorem 3.2. We start with some notations and definitions before stating the main result of this section.

For every vertex $u \in V(G) \setminus \{s, t\}$, we denote by \mathcal{P}_{su} (\mathcal{P}_{tu}) the set of induced paths from s to u (t to u). We assume the path-sets are arbitrarily ordered where $\ell_{su} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} |\mathcal{P}_{su}|$, and $\ell_{tu} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} |\mathcal{P}_{tu}|$.

$$\mathcal{P}_{su} = \{P_1^{su}, \dots, P_{\ell_{su}}^{su}\} \quad \mathcal{P}_{tu} = \{P_1^{tu}, \dots, P_{\ell_{tu}}^{tu}\} \quad (8)$$

Consider the induced paths $P_i^{su} \in \mathcal{P}_{su}$ and $P_j^{tv} \in \mathcal{P}_{tv}$ from s to u and v to t respectively. Denote by $G_{ij}^{su,tv}$ the graph that results from G by contracting all edges on the path P_i^{su} to vertex s , and all edges on the path P_j^{tv} to vertex t . When s, u, t, v are clear from the context, we refer to this graph as G_{ij} . For a pair $u, v \in V(G) \setminus \{s, t\}$, we define the sets of graphs $\mathcal{G}_1(u, v)$ and $\mathcal{G}_2(u, v)$ as follows:

$$\mathcal{G}_1(u, v) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{G_{ij}^{su,tv} : i \in [1, \ell_{su}], j \in [1, \ell_{tv}]\} \quad \mathcal{G}_2(u, v) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{G_{ij}^{sv,tu} : i \in [1, \ell_{sv}], j \in [1, \ell_{tu}]\} \quad (9)$$

We recall that ℓ denotes the maximal branch-depth among all induced paths in G having an endpoint in $\{s, t\}$. Therefore, by Lemma 2.2, it holds that $|\mathcal{G}_i(u, v)| \leq 3^{\frac{2\ell}{3}}$ for $i \in \{1, 2\}$ (see (9)), and that the set of graphs \mathcal{G}_1 and \mathcal{G}_2 can be generated in time $O^*(3^{\frac{2\ell}{3}})$. In the rest of this section, we prove the following Theorem that allows us to enumerate the minimal st -separators that cross a certain $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$ in ranked order, and in FPT-delay.

Theorem 4.1. Let $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$ where $u, v \in S$, and $(u, v) \notin E(G)$. Denote by G' the graph that results from G by adding the edge (u, v) . That is, $E(G') = E(G) \cup \{(u, v)\}$. Then:

$$\mathcal{S}_1(u, v) = \bigcup_{H \in \mathcal{G}_1(u, v)} \mathcal{S}_{st}(H), \quad \mathcal{S}_2(u, v) = \bigcup_{H \in \mathcal{G}_2(u, v)} \mathcal{S}_{st}(H), \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{S}_{st}(G') = \mathcal{S}_3(u, v) \cup \mathcal{S}_4(u, v) \quad (10)$$

where $\mathcal{G}_1(u, v)$ and $\mathcal{G}_2(u, v)$ are defined in (9).

The main challenge is to prove that $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G') = \mathcal{S}_3(u, v) \cup \mathcal{S}_4(u, v)$. We do so in a series of lemmas that, together with Lemma 4.1 below, prove Theorem 4.1.

Lemma 4.1. Let $u, v \in V(G)$. The following holds:

$$\mathcal{S}_1(u, v) = \bigcup_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq \ell_{su} \\ 1 \leq j \leq \ell_{tv}}} \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_{ij}) = \bigcup_{H \in \mathcal{G}_1(u, v)} \mathcal{S}_{st}(H) \quad (11)$$

where G_{ij} denotes the graph that results from contracting all the edges in $P_i^{su} \in \mathcal{P}_{su}$ and $P_j^{tv} \in \mathcal{P}_{tv}$ to vertices s and t respectively. Symmetrically, this holds for $\mathcal{S}_2(u, v)$ as well.

Proof. We prove for $\mathcal{S}_1(u, v)$, and $\mathcal{S}_2(u, v)$ is identical. Let $S \in \mathcal{S}_1(u, v)$. Therefore, $u \in C_s(G, S)$ and $v \in C_t(G, S)$. Therefore, there is an induced path P_{su} from s to u in $G[C_s(G, S)]$ such that $V(P_{su}) \cap S = \emptyset$, and likewise there is an induced vt -path P_{vt} in $G[C_t(G, S)]$ such that $V(P_{vt}) \cap S = \emptyset$. In particular, S is a minimal $V(P_{su}), V(P_{tv})$ -separator (see Section 2.2). By Theorem 2.4, $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G')$ where G' is the graph that results from contracting all edges of P_{su} into vertex s and all edges of P_{tv} into vertex t . Since, by definition, $P_{su} \in \mathcal{P}_{su}$, and $P_{tv} \in \mathcal{P}_{tv}$ (see (11)), then $S \in \bigcup_{\substack{1 \leq i \leq \ell_{su} \\ 1 \leq j \leq \ell_{tv}}} \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_{ij})$.

For the other direction, let $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_{ij})$. Since the paths $P_i \in \mathcal{P}_{su}$ and $P_j \in \mathcal{P}_{tv}$ are, by definition, connected components, then by Theorem 2.4, it holds that S is a minimal $V(P_i), V(P_j)$ -separator in G . Let C_A and C_B denote the connected components of $\mathcal{C}_G(S)$ containing P_i and P_j respectively. Since S is a minimal $V(P_i), V(P_j)$ -separator, then C_A and C_B are full components with respect to S . Since $\{s, u\} \subseteq V(P_i) \subseteq C_A$, and $\{t, v\} \subseteq V(P_j) \subseteq C_B$, then C_A and C_B are full connected components containing s and t respectively. Hence, by Lemma 2.1, $S \in \mathcal{S}_1(u, v)$. \square

Lemma 4.2. Let $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$, and let $u, v \in S$. Let G' be the graph where $\mathbf{V}(G') = \mathbf{V}(G)$, and $\mathbf{E}(G') = \mathbf{E}(G) \cup \{(u, v)\}$. Then $\mathcal{S}_3(u, v) \cup \mathcal{S}_4(u, v) \subseteq \mathcal{S}_{st}(G')$.

Proof. Let $S \in \mathcal{S}_3(u, v)$. That is, $\exists C \in \mathcal{C}_G(S)$ such that $\{u, v\} \subseteq C \cup S$. Following the addition of the edge (u, v) , we have that $C_s(G, S) = C_s(G', S)$ and $C_t(G, S) = C_t(G', S)$, and these connected components remain separated in $G'[\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus S]$. Since $C_s(G, S)$ and $C_t(G, S)$ are full connected components in G , then $C_s(G', S)$ and $C_t(G', S)$ are full connected components in G' . By Lemma 2.1, $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G')$.

Now, let $S \in \mathcal{S}_4(u, v)$, and let $C_u, C_v \in \mathcal{C}_G(S)$ denote the connected components containing u and v respectively. Since $\{C_u, C_v\} \neq \{C_s(G, S), C_t(G, S)\}$, then we can assume wlog that $C_u \notin \{C_s(G, S), C_t(G, S)\}$. Therefore, no edge is added between $C_s(G, S)$ and $C_t(G, S)$ in G' , and hence s and t remain separated in $G'[\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus S]$. That is, there exist two distinct connected components $C_s(G', S), C_t(G', S) \in \mathcal{C}_{G'}(S)$ containing s and t , respectively. Since $\mathbf{E}(G') \supseteq \mathbf{E}(G)$, then $C_s(G, S) \subseteq C_s(G', S)$, and $C_t(G, S) \subseteq C_t(G', S)$. But this means that $C_s(G', S)$ and $C_t(G', S)$ are full components containing s and t respectively in $G'[\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus S]$. Therefore, by Lemma 2.1, we have that $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G')$. \square

Proposition 4.1. Let $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$, where $u, v \in S$. Then $uv \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(H_{uv})$, where $H_{uv} \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} G[\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus (S \setminus uv)]$.

Proof. Since $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$, then uv separates s from t in H_{uv} . Assume, by way of contradiction, that $uv \notin \mathcal{S}_{st}(H_{uv})$, and let $T \subset uv$ be an st -separator in H_{uv} . But then, $(S - uv) \cup T \subset (S - uv) \cup uv = S$ separates s from t in G , which means that $S \notin \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$, and we arrive at a contradiction. \square

Lemma 4.3. Let $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$, where $u, v \in S$, and $(u, v) \notin \mathbf{E}(G)$. Define $H \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} G[\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus (S \setminus uv)]$. If $T \in \mathcal{S}_1(u, v) \cup \mathcal{S}_2(u, v)$ (see (2) and (3)), then there exists a subset $T' \subseteq T$ such that:

$$T' \in \mathcal{S}(H) \quad \text{and} \quad T' \cap C_s(H, uv) \neq \emptyset \quad \text{and} \quad T' \cap C_t(H, uv) \neq \emptyset \quad (12)$$

where $C_s(H, uv)$ and $C_t(H, uv)$ are the full connected components of H containing s and t , respectively.

Proof. First, by Proposition 4.1, we have that $uv \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(H)$, and in particular that $uv \in \mathcal{S}(H)$.

Suppose wlog that $T \in \mathcal{S}_1(u, v)$. That is, $u \in C_s(G, T)$ and $v \in C_t(G, T)$. By Lemma 2.1, it holds that T is a minimal uv -separator in G . That is, $T \in \mathcal{S}_{uv}(G)$. Since H is a subgraph of G , then $T \cap \mathbf{V}(H)$ is a uv -separator in H . Let $T' \subseteq T \cap \mathbf{V}(H)$ be a minimal uv -separator in H . So, we have that $uv \in \mathcal{S}(H)$, $T' \in \mathcal{S}(H)$, and T' separates u from v in H . By definition, we have that $T' \# uv$ in H .

Since $\{u, v\} \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(H)$, then there exist two internally-disjoint paths between u and v : P_1 contained entirely in $C_s(H, uv)$, and P_2 contained entirely in $C_t(H, uv)$. Since $T' \in \mathcal{S}_{uv}(H)$, and since $T' \subseteq T \subseteq \mathbf{V}(G) \setminus \{s, t, u, v\}$, then there exist vertices $v_1 \in T' \cap \mathbf{V}(P_1)$ and $v_2 \in T' \cap \mathbf{V}(P_2)$ where $v_1 \notin \{s, u\}$ and $v_2 \notin \{v, t\}$. Therefore, $v_1 \in T' \cap C_s(H, uv) \neq \emptyset$ and $v_2 \in T' \cap C_t(H, uv) \neq \emptyset$. \square

Lemma 4.4. Let $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$, and let $u, v \in S$. Let G' be the graph where $\mathbf{V}(G') = \mathbf{V}(G)$, and $\mathbf{E}(G') = \mathbf{E}(G) \cup \{(u, v)\}$. Then $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G') \subseteq \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$.

Proof. If $(u, v) \in \mathbf{E}(G)$, then $G' = G$, and the claim is immediate. We further observe that $S \in \mathcal{S}_3(u, v)$ (see (4)), and hence $S \in \mathcal{S}_3(u, v) \cup \mathcal{S}_4(u, v) \neq \emptyset$.

Let $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G')$. Since $\mathbf{E}(G) \subseteq \mathbf{E}(G')$, then T is an st -separator in G . Suppose, by way of contradiction, that $T \notin \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$. Let $J \subset T$ such that $J \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$. Then $J \in \mathcal{S}_1^G(u, v) \cup \dots \cup \mathcal{S}_4^G(u, v)$ (see (6)). By Lemma 4.2, we have that $\mathcal{S}_3^G(u, v) \cup \mathcal{S}_4^G(u, v) \subseteq \mathcal{S}_{st}(G')$. Consequently, it must

hold that $J \in \mathcal{S}_1^G(u, v) \cup \mathcal{S}_2^G(u, v)$. Otherwise, $J \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G')$, contradicting the assumption that $J \subset T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G')$.

Let $H \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} G[\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus (S \setminus uv)]$ where, by Proposition 4.1, $uv \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(H)$. Since $J \in \mathcal{S}_1^G(u, v) \cup \mathcal{S}_2^G(u, v)$, then by Lemma 4.3, there exists a subset $J' \subseteq J \subset T$ where $J' \in \mathcal{S}(H)$, $J' \cap C_s(H, uv) \neq \emptyset$, and $J' \cap C_t(H, uv) \neq \emptyset$. Now, consider the graph H' that results from H by adding the edge (u, v) , or equivalently, from G' by removing vertices $S \setminus uv$. Clearly, it holds that $C_s(H, uv) = C_s(H', uv)$ and $C_t(H, uv) = C_t(H', uv)$. Therefore, $J' \cap C_s(H', uv) \neq \emptyset$, and $J' \cap C_t(H', uv) \neq \emptyset$. By definition of crossing minimal separators, this means that $J' \# uv$ in H' . But this is impossible because uv is a clique-minimal-separator in H' . Consequently, for every $J' \subseteq J$ where $J' \in \mathcal{S}(H)$, it holds that $J' \parallel uv$. But then, by Lemma 4.3, $J \notin \mathcal{S}_1(u, v) \cup \mathcal{S}_2(u, v)$, and we arrive at a contradiction. \square

Proof of Theorem 4.1. The fact that $\mathcal{S}_i(u, v) = \bigcup_{H \in \mathcal{G}_i(u, v)} \mathcal{S}_{st}(H)$ for $i \in \{1, 2\}$ follows directly from Lemma 4.1. That $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G') = \mathcal{S}_3^G(u, v) \cup \mathcal{S}_4^G(u, v)$ follows from Lemma 4.2, that shows that $\mathcal{S}_3^G(u, v) \cup \mathcal{S}_4^G(u, v) \subseteq \mathcal{S}_{st}(G')$, and Lemma 4.4, which shows that $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G') \subseteq \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$. Since $(u, v) \in \mathbf{E}(G')$, then $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G') \cap (\mathcal{S}_1^G(u, v) \cup \mathcal{S}_2^G(u, v)) = \emptyset$, and hence, by (6), that $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G') \subseteq \mathcal{S}_3^G(u, v) \cup \mathcal{S}_4^G(u, v)$. Combined, we get that $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G') = \mathcal{S}_3^G(u, v) \cup \mathcal{S}_4^G(u, v)$.

Lemma 4.5. Let $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$ and let $\{(u_1, v_1), \dots, (u_k, v_k)\}$ be a set of non-edges of $G[S]$. Let G' be the graph where $\mathbf{V}(G') = \mathbf{V}(G)$ and $\mathbf{E}(G') = \mathbf{E}(G) \cup \bigcup_{i=1}^k (u_i, v_i)$. Then:

$$\mathcal{S}_{st}(G') = \bigcap_{i=1}^k (\mathcal{S}_3^G(u_i, v_i) \cup \mathcal{S}_4^G(u_i, v_i)) \quad (13)$$

The proof of Lemma 4.5 applies Lemma 4.4 by induction on k , and is deferred to Appendix C.

Theorem 4.2. Let $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$, and let $\{(u_1, v_1), \dots, (u_k, v_k)\}$ be a fixed order of the set of non-edges of $G[S]$. Then:

$$\{T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G) : T \# S\} = \bigsqcup_{i=1}^k \left(\bigcup_{H \in \mathcal{G}_1(u_i, v_i)} \mathcal{S}_{st}(H^{i-1}) \right) \uplus \bigsqcup_{i=1}^k \left(\bigcup_{H \in \mathcal{G}_2(u_i, v_i)} \mathcal{S}_{st}(H^{i-1}) \right) \quad (14)$$

where H^{i-1} is the graph that results from H by adding edges $\{(u_1, v_1), \dots, (u_{i-1}, v_{i-1})\}$ to H .

Proof. We prove that

$$\bigcup_{H \in \mathcal{G}_p(u_i, v_i)} \mathcal{S}_{st}(H^{i-1}) = \mathcal{S}_p^G(u_i, v_i) \cap \bigcap_{j=1}^{i-1} \mathcal{S}_{34}^G(u_j, v_j) \quad \text{for } p \in \{1, 2\} \quad (15)$$

and the result then follows from Theorem 3.2. We prove for $p = 1$, and the case for $p = 2$ is identical. Denote by G^{i-1} the graph that results from G by adding edges $\{(u_1, v_1), \dots, (u_{i-1}, v_{i-1})\}$.

Let $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(H^{i-1})$ where $H \in \mathcal{G}_1(u_i, v_i)$. By definition, H is the graph that results from G by contracting all edges in an induced path $P \in \mathcal{P}_{su_i}$ and all edges in an induced path $Q \in \mathcal{P}_{tv_i}$. Since P and Q are connected, then by Theorem 2.4, T is a minimal $\mathbf{V}(P), \mathbf{V}(Q)$ -separator in G^{i-1} . Since $s, u_i \in \mathbf{V}(P)$ and $v_i, t \in \mathbf{V}(Q)$, then $T \in \mathcal{S}_1^{G^{i-1}}(u_i, v_i)$. By Lemma 4.5, $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G^{i-1}) = \bigcap_{j=1}^{i-1} \mathcal{S}_{34}^G(u_j, v_j)$. Since $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G^{i-1}) \subseteq \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$, then $\mathcal{S}_1^{G^{i-1}}(u_i, v_i) \subseteq \mathcal{S}_1^G(u_i, v_i)$. Consequently, we get that $T \in \mathcal{S}_1^G(u_i, v_i) \cap \bigcap_{j=1}^{i-1} \mathcal{S}_{34}^G(u_j, v_j)$

Now, let $T \in \mathcal{S}_1^G(u_i, v_i) \cap \bigcap_{j=1}^{i-1} \mathcal{S}_{34}^G(u_j, v_j)$. Since $T \in \mathcal{S}_1^G(u_i, v_i)$, then $u_i \in C_s(G, T)$ and $v_i \in C_t(G, T)$. Hence, there exist two induced paths $P_1 \in \mathcal{P}_{su_i}$ from u_i to s in $G[C_s(G, T)]$ and

$P_2 \in \mathcal{P}_{tv_i}$ from v_i to t in $G[C_t(G, T)]$. Since $T \in \bigcap_{j=1}^{i-1} \mathcal{S}_{34}^G(u_j, v_j)$, then by Lemma 4.5, it holds that $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G^{i-1})$. In particular, this means that $C_s(G, T)$ and $C_t(G, T)$ remain separated in $G^{i-1}[\mathbb{V}(G) \setminus T]$. Hence, $C_s(G^{i-1}, T) \supseteq C_s(G, T) \supseteq \mathbb{V}(P_1)$ and $C_t(G^{i-1}, T) \supseteq C_t(G, T) \supseteq \mathbb{V}(P_2)$. Since $C_s(G^{i-1}, T)$ and $C_t(G^{i-1}, T)$ are full connected components associated with T in G^{i-1} , then T is a minimal $\mathbb{V}(P_1), \mathbb{V}(P_2)$ -separator in G^{i-1} . By Theorem 2.4, it holds that $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(H^{i-1})$ where H^{i-1} is the graph that results from G^{i-1} by contracting all edges of P_1 (P_2). Or equivalently, merging all nodes on P_1 (P_2) to vertex s (t). Since $P_1 \in \mathcal{P}_{su_i}$ and $P_2 \in \mathcal{P}_{tv_i}$, this proves the claim. \square

5 Characterizing Parallel Minimal st -separators Using Graphs

Let $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$. In this section, we describe a pair of graphs that we refer to as $G_s[S]$ and $G_t[S]$, that have the following properties: (1) $\{T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G) : T \parallel S\} = \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_s[S]) \cup \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_t[S])$, and (2) $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G_s[S]) \cap \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_t[S]) = \{S\}$. This characterization is applied in the ranked enumeration algorithm. We start with the following property, presented in the survey paper by Heggernes [22], that gathers related results by Berry [3], Bouchitté and Todinca [7], Kloks et al. [27], and Parra and Scheffler [37].

Theorem 5.1. ([22]) Let G be a graph, and $\mathcal{P} \subseteq \mathcal{S}(G)$ an arbitrary set of pairwise parallel minimal separators of G . Obtain G' by saturating every separator in \mathcal{P} (i.e., $\mathbb{E}(G') = \mathbb{E}(G) \cup \bigcup_{S \in \mathcal{P}} \{(u, v) : u, v \in S\}$). Then the following holds.

1. A clique minimal separator of G does not cross any minimal separator of G' .
2. Every $S \in \mathcal{P}$ is a clique minimal separator of G' .
3. Any clique minimal separator of G is a minimal separator of G' .
4. Any minimal separator of G' is a minimal separator of G .
5. The induced graphs $G[\mathbb{V}(G) \setminus S]$ and $G'[\mathbb{V}(G') \setminus S]$ have the same set of connected components for each minimal separator $S \in \mathcal{S}(G')$.
6. The induced graphs $G[\mathbb{V}(G) \setminus S]$ and $G'[\mathbb{V}(G') \setminus S]$ have the same set of full components for each minimal separator $S \in \mathcal{S}(G')$.
7. Any set of pairwise parallel minimal separators of G' is a set of pairwise parallel minimal separators of G .

Lemma 5.1. Let $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$, and let G' denote the graph where $G[S]$ has been saturated to a clique. Then the following holds:

$$\mathcal{S}_{st}(G') = \{T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G) : T \text{ is parallel to } S\} \quad (16)$$

Proof follows by application of the properties in Theorem 5.1, and is deferred to Appendix C.

Lemma 5.2. Let $S, T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$ where S and T are parallel minimal st -separators. Then $T \subseteq C_s(G, S) \cup S$ or $T \subseteq C_t(G, S) \cup S$, where $C_s(G, S)$ and $C_t(G, S)$ are the full connected components associated with S .

Proof. Since S and T are parallel then, by definition, there is a single connected component $C_T \in \mathcal{C}_G(S)$ such that $T \cap C_T \neq \emptyset$, and hence $T \subseteq C_T \cup S$. It is left to show that $C_T \in \{C_s(G, S), C_t(G, S)\}$. Suppose, by way of contradiction, that $C_T \notin \{C_s(G, S), C_t(G, S)\}$. Let $H \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} G[C_s(G, S) \cup S \cup C_t(G, S)]$. Since $C_T \notin \{C_s(G, S), C_t(G, S)\}$, then $T \cap (C_s(G, S) \cup S \cup C_t(G, S)) = T \cap S \subset S$. Since $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$ and H is a subgraph of G , then $T \cap \mathbb{V}(H)$ separates s and t also in H . In particular, $T \cap \mathbb{V}(H) \subset S$ separates s and t in H . But then, $S \notin \mathcal{S}_{st}(H)$, contradicting the fact that $C_s(G, S)$ and $C_t(G, S)$ are the full connected components associated with S in G . Therefore, $C_T \in \{C_s(G, S), C_t(G, S)\}$. \square

We recall that merging a subset of vertices $T \subseteq \mathbf{V}(G)$ into a single vertex w is the operation of deleting all vertices in T , and adding an edge between w and every vertex in $N_G(T)$.

Definition 5.1. Let $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$, and let $C_s(G, S)$ and $C_t(G, S)$ denote the full connected components containing s and t , respectively. Let H be the graph that results from saturating S to a clique: $\mathbf{E}(H) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathbf{E}(G) \cup \{(u, v) : \{u, v\} \subseteq S\}$. We denote by $G_s[S]$ the graph that results from H by merging the vertices $C_t(G, S)$ to vertex t , and by $G_t[S]$ the graph that results from H by merging the vertices $C_s(G, S)$ to vertex s . Formally:

$$\mathbf{V}(G_s[S]) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} C_s(G, S) \cup S \cup \{t\} \quad \mathbf{E}(G_s[S]) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathbf{E}(H[C_s(G, S) \cup S]) \cup \{(u, t) : u \in S\} \quad (17)$$

$$\mathbf{V}(G_t[S]) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} C_t(G, S) \cup S \cup \{s\} \quad \mathbf{E}(G_t[S]) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathbf{E}(H[C_t(G, S) \cup S]) \cup \{(u, s) : u \in S\} \quad (18)$$

Lemma 5.3. Let $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$ be a clique-minimal st -separator of G , and let $G_s[S]$ and $G_t[S]$ be the graphs as defined in Definition 5.1. Then:

$$\mathcal{S}_{st}(G) = \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_s[S]) \cup \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_t[S]) \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_s[S]) \cap \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_t[S]) = \{S\} \quad (19)$$

Proof. Let $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G) \setminus \{S\}$. Since S is a clique in G , then by item 1 of Theorem 5.1, S and T are parallel in G . By Lemma 5.2, it holds that $T \subseteq C_s(G, S) \cup S$ or $T \subseteq C_t(G, S) \cup S$. WLOG assume the former. We claim that $C_s(G, T) \subseteq C_s(G, S)$. If not, then there is a vertex $w \in S \cup (\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus (S \cup C_s(G, S)))$, such that $w \in C_s(G, T)$. If $w \notin S$, then $w \in C$ for some $C \in \mathcal{C}_G(S) \setminus \{C_s(G, S)\}$. Since $w \in C_s(G, T)$, we let P_{ws} be a path from s to w in $G[C_s(G, T)]$. Since $w \in C$ where $C \neq C_s(G, S)$, then every path from s to w passes through a vertex in S . In particular, P_{ws} passes through a vertex in S . Since $\mathbf{V}(P_{ws}) \subseteq C_s(G, T)$, and $\mathbf{V}(P_{ws}) \cap S \neq \emptyset$, then $C_s(G, T) \cap S \neq \emptyset$. Therefore, if $w \in S \cup (\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus (S \cup C_s(G, S)))$, such that $w \in C_s(G, T)$, then there is a vertex $v \in S$, such that $v \in C_s(G, T)$. So, let $v \in S \cap C_s(G, T)$.

Since $v \in S$ where $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$, there is a path $p = v, w_1, \dots, w_r, t$ from v to t in which all vertices $\{w_1, \dots, w_r, t\}$ belong to $C_t(G, S)$. Since T is a minimal st -separator and $v \in C_s(G, T)$, it means that $T \cap C_t(G, S) \neq \emptyset$. But then, $T \not\subseteq S \cup C_s(G, S)$, which is a contradiction. Therefore, $C_s(G, T) \subseteq C_s(G, S)$. Since $C_s(G, T) \subseteq C_s(G, S)$, then $C_s(G, T) \cap C_t(G, S) = \emptyset$. Hence, T minimally-separates s from every vertex in $C_t(G, S)$, and in particular, T is a minimal st -separator in $G_s[S]$ (i.e., where $C_t(G, S)$ was merged into a single vertex t). That is, $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_s[S])$. Symmetrically, if $T \subseteq C_t(G, S) \cup S$, then we get that $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_t[S])$.

For the other direction, let $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_s[S])$. Since t is the result of merging $C_t(G, S)$ into vertex t , and since $G[C_t(G, S)]$ and $\{s\}$ are connected components of G , then by Theorem 2.4, we get that T is a minimal $\{s\}, C_t(G, S)$ -separator. Since $t \in C_t(G, S)$, then $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$. Symmetrically, if $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_t[S])$, we get that $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$. This proves that $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G) = \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_s[S]) \cup \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_t[S])$.

Observe that since $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$ then $S = N_G(C_s(G, S)) = N_G(C_t(G, S))$. Therefore, $N_{G_t[S]}(s) = S$ and $N_{G_s[S]}(t) = S$. Therefore, $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_s[S]) \cap \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_t[S])$. Suppose, by way of contradiction, that there is a $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$, distinct from S , such that $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_s[S]) \cap \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_t[S])$. Since $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_s[S])$, then $T \subseteq \mathbf{V}(G_s[S]) \setminus \{s, t\} = (S \cup C_s(G, S)) \setminus \{s\}$. Since $S, T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$, then $T \not\subseteq S$. Therefore, there is a vertex $w \in T \cap C_s(G, S)$ where $w \neq s$. If $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_t[S])$, then $T \subseteq \mathbf{V}(G_t[S]) = S \cup C_t(G, S) \setminus \{s, t\}$. But this would mean that $w \in C_t(G, S)$ and that $w \in C_s(G, S) \cap C_t(G, S)$, which is a contradiction to the fact that $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$. Hence $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G_s[S]) \cap \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_t[S]) = \{S\}$. \square

Corollary 5.1. Let $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$ be a minimal st -separator of G (that is not necessarily a clique), and let $G_s[S]$ and $G_t[S]$ be the graphs as in Definition 5.1. Then:

$$\{T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G) : T \parallel S\} = \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_s[S]) \cup \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_t[S]) \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_s[S]) \cap \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_t[S]) = \{S\} \quad (20)$$

Proof. Let H be the graph that results from G by saturating S to a clique. By item 2 of Theorem 5.1, we have that S is a clique-minimal separator of H . By applying Lemma 5.3 to $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(H)$ and H , we get that $\mathcal{S}_{st}(H) = \mathcal{S}_{st}(H_s[S]) \cup \mathcal{S}_{st}(H_t[S])$ and $\mathcal{S}_{st}(H_s[S]) \cap \mathcal{S}_{st}(H_t[S]) = \{S\}$. Observe that by definition 5.1, it holds that $H_s[S] = G_s[S]$ and $H_t[S] = G_t[S]$. Therefore,

$$\mathcal{S}_{st}(H) = \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_s[S]) \cup \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_t[S]) \quad \text{and} \quad \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_s[S]) \cap \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_t[S]) = \{S\}. \quad (21)$$

We now show that $\mathcal{S}_{st}(H) = \{T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G) : T \parallel S\}$, and this will prove the claim. By item 4 of Theorem 5.1, every minimal separator of H is a minimal separator of G . Hence, $\mathcal{S}_{st}(H) \subseteq \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$. By item 1 of Theorem 5.1, every minimal separator of H is parallel to S . Therefore, $\mathcal{S}_{st}(H) \subseteq \{T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G) : T \parallel S\}$.

We show that $\mathcal{S}_{st}(H) = \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_s[S]) \cup \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_t[S]) \supseteq \{T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G) : T \parallel S\}$. Take any $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$ such that $T \parallel S$. By Lemma 5.2, it holds that $T \subseteq C_T \cup S$ where $C_T \in \{C_s(G, S), C_t(G, S)\}$. If $C_T \neq C_t(G, S)$, then $T \cap C_t(G, S) = \emptyset$, and thus $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_s[S])$. Otherwise, if $C_T = C_t(G, S)$, then $T \subseteq C_t(G, S) \cup S$, and hence $T \cap C_s(G, S) = \emptyset$, and therefore, $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_t[S])$. Therefore, $\{T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G) : T \parallel S\} \subseteq \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_s[S]) \cup \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_t[S])$. Overall, we have that $\mathcal{S}_{st}(H) = \{T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G) : T \parallel S\}$. The result follows from the fact that $\mathcal{S}_{st}(H) = \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_s[S]) \cup \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_t[S])$ (e.g., see (21)). \square

5.1 Finding The Smallest Parallel Minimal st -separator

A minimal st -separator S is said to be *close to s* (or *t*) if $S \subseteq N_G(s)$ (or $S \subseteq N_G(t)$). The following Lemma about close minimal separators was proved by Kloks and Kratsch [26].

Lemma 5.4. ([26]) Let s and t be non-adjacent vertices in G . Then there is a unique minimal st -separator contained in $N_G(s)$ ($N_G(t)$).

Let J_s (J_t) denote the unique minimal st -separator close to s (t). We now consider the problem of finding the minimal st -separator of smallest size that is distinct from J_s and J_t .

Lemma 5.5. Let $J_s \subseteq N_G(s)$ be the unique minimal st -separator that is close to s . Then $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G) \setminus \{J_s\} = \bigcup_{v \in J_s} \mathcal{S}_{st}(G^{(sv)})$ where $G^{(sv)}$ is the graph that results from merging the neighbors s and v to vertex s .

Proof. Let $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G) \setminus \{J_s\}$. Since J_s and T are distinct minimal st -separators, then $J_s \not\subseteq T$. Therefore, there is a vertex $v \in J_s \setminus T \subseteq N_G(s) \setminus T$. Since $v \in N_G(s) \setminus T$, then $v \in C_s(G, T)$. Therefore, T is a minimal sv, t -separator. By Theorem 2.4, $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G^{(sv)})$.

Let $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G^{(sv)})$ for some $v \in J_s \subseteq N_G(s)$. By Theorem 2.4, T is a minimal $\{sv\}, \{t\}$ -separator, and in particular, $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G) \setminus \{J_s\}$. \square

Corollary 5.2. Let $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$, and let $G_s[S]$, and $G_t[S]$ be the graphs defined in (17) and (18) respectively. Then:

$$\{T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G) : T \parallel S\} \setminus \{S\} = \bigcup_{v \in S} \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_s[S]^{(tv)}) \cup \bigcup_{v \in S} \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_t[S]^{(sv)}) \quad (22)$$

Proof. By definition 5.1, we have that S is a minimal st -separator of $G_s[S]$ that is close to t (i.e., $S \subseteq N_{G_s[S]}(t)$), and S is a minimal st -separator of $G_t[S]$ that is close to s (i.e., $S \subseteq N_{G_t[S]}(s)$). By Lemma 5.5, we have that $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G_s[S]) \setminus \{S\} = \bigcup_{v \in S} \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_s^{(tv)}[S])$, and $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G_t[S]) \setminus \{S\} = \bigcup_{v \in S} \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_t^{(sv)}[S])$. From Corollary 5.1, we get that $\{T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G) : T \parallel S\} \setminus \{S\} = (\mathcal{S}_{st}(G_s[S]) \setminus \{S\}) \cup (\mathcal{S}_{st}(G_t[S]) \setminus \{S\})$. This completes the proof. \square

We now consider the following problem. Let G be a graph where $N_G(s) \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$ or $N_G(t) \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$. We wish to find the minimum-weight st -separator $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$ of G , such that $T \notin \{N_G(s), N_G(t)\}$. Based on Corollary 5.2, we devise an Algorithm that receives as input an undirected graph G , a pair of vertices $\{s, t\}$, and a label $\mathbf{lbl} \in \{\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{t}, \mathbf{st}, _ \}$ indicating whether to return the minimum-weight st -separator that is distinct from $N_G(s)$, $N_G(t)$, or both $N_G(s)$ and $N_G(t)$, respectively. If $\mathbf{lbl} = _$, then the algorithm simply returns a minimum-weight st -separator of G . The assumption made by the procedure is that if $\mathbf{s} \in \mathbf{lbl}$ ($\mathbf{t} \in \mathbf{lbl}$), then $N_G(s) \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$ ($N_G(t) \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$). Since this Algorithm is a straightforward implementation of Corollary 5.2, we defer the details to Appendix C, where we also show that it runs in time $O(n^2T(n, m))$ (Proposition C.1).

A Minimal Separators and Chordless st -paths

In this section we show that given a set $I \subseteq V(G)$, it is NP-hard to decide whether there exists a minimal st -separator $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$ such that $I \subset S$. We prove this by showing a reduction from the problem of 3 -in-a-path that asks whether there is an induced path containing three given terminals. Bienstock [4] has shown that deciding whether two terminals belong to an induced cycle is NP-hard. From this, it is easy to show that the three-in-a-path problem is NP-hard even for graphs whose degree is at most three [13]. In fact, even deciding whether there is such a path of length at most k was shown to be $W[1]$ -complete with respect to the length parameter k [20]. The related problem, of three-in-a-tree for deciding whether there is an induced tree containing three terminals, is in PTIME [31].

Theorem A.1. Let $v \in V(G)$. There exists a minimal st -separator that includes v if and only if there exists a chordless st -path through v .

Proof. Let S be a minimal st -separator in G that includes v , and let $C_s(G, S)$, $C_t(G, S)$ denote the connected components of $G[V(G) \setminus S]$ that contain s and t respectively. By Lemma 2.1, there exists a path from s to v where all the internal vertices of P_{sv} belong to $C_s(G, S)$. Let P_{sv} denote the shortest such path. Likewise, let P_{vt} denote the shortest path from v to t where all internal vertices belong to $C_t(G, S)$. Clearly, P_{sv} and P_{vt} are both chordless paths. Since $C_s(G, S) \cap C_t(G, S) = \emptyset$, then $V(P_{sv}) \cap V(P_{vt}) = \{v\}$. Since $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$, then there are no edges between vertices in $C_s(G, S)$ and vertices in $C_t(G, S)$. Consequently, there are no edges between vertices in $V(P_{sv})$ and $V(P_{vt})$. Therefore, the path $P_{sv}P_{vt}$ is a chordless st -path that passes through v . In other words, if $v \in S$, then there is an induced st -path through v .

Let $P = s, a_1, \dots, a_k, v, b_1, \dots, b_\ell, t$ denote a simple, chordless st -path through v . If $v \in N_G(s)$ ($v \in N_G(t)$), then $k = 0$ ($\ell = 0$). Merge all vertices of the sub-path $P_a \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (s, a_1, \dots, a_k)$ into a new merged vertex s' , and all vertices of the path $P_b \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (b_1, \dots, b_\ell, t)$ into a new merged vertex t' . Since P is simple, then P_a and P_b are vertex-disjoint. Since P is chordless, then there are no edges between (a_i, b_j) for all $i \in [1, k]$ and all $j \in [1, \ell]$. Therefore, following the contraction, s' and t' are not adjacent in the new graph G' , and hence separable.

Let S' be a minimal $s't'$ -separator in G' . By construction, $v \in N_{G'}(s') \cap N_{G'}(t')$, and hence $v \in S'$. It is left to show that S' is a minimal st -separator of G . Let $C_{s'}(S', G')$ and $C_{t'}(S', G')$ denote the full connected components of $G'[V(G') \setminus S']$ containing s' and t' respectively. Define $D_s(S', G) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (C_{s'}(S', G') \setminus s') \cup \{s, a_1, \dots, a_k\}$ and $D_t(S', G) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (C_{t'}(S', G') \setminus t') \cup \{b_1, \dots, b_\ell, t\}$. By construction, $D_s(S', G)$ and $D_t(S', G)$ are disjoint, and $G[D_s(S', G)]$ ($G[D_t(S', G)]$) are connected. Since $C_{s'}(S', G')$ and $C_{t'}(S', G')$ are full components of S' in G' , then by definition of the merge operator, $D_s(S', G)$ and $D_t(S', G)$ are full components of S' in G . By Lemma 2.1, S' is a minimal st -separator of G . \square

Theorem A.1 provides a characterization of when a vertex v is included in a minimal separator. By reduction from the 3-in-a-path problem we conclude that deciding whether there is a minimal st -separator containing a subset I is an NP-complete problem.

B An FPT-Delay Algorithm for Ranked Enumeration of Minimal st -separators

In this section, we put everything together, and present the algorithm for enumerating the minimal st -separators of G in ascending order of cardinality. We will require the following simple lemma.

Lemma B.1. Let $J_s \subseteq N_G(s)$ denote the minimal st -separator close to s . Let $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$ be distinct from J_s . Then $J_s \parallel T$. Symmetrically, $J_t \parallel T$.

Proof. Since $J_s \subseteq N_G(s)$, then $J_s \subseteq C_s(G, T) \cup T$. By definition, $J_s \parallel T$. \square

The algorithm starts by finding a minimum-weight st -separator S (line 5), and pushing the triple $\langle G, S, _ \rangle$ to a sorted queue Q (line 6). The algorithm proceeds by repeatedly extracting from the queue Q the triple $\langle G, S, \mathbf{1b1} \rangle$, where S has smallest weight. The algorithm constructs graphs $G_s[S]$ and $G_t[S]$ (see Definition 5.1) in line 15. By Corollary 5.1, we have that $\{T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G) : T \parallel S\} = \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_s[S]) \cup \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_t[S])$, and that $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G_s[S]) \cap \mathcal{S}_{st}(G_t[S]) = \{S\}$. In particular, by definition of $G_s[S]$ ($G_t[S]$), we have that $S = N_{G_s[S]}(t)$, $S = N_{G_t[S]}(s)$, and that $S \in \mathcal{L}_{st}(G_t[S]) \cap \mathcal{L}_{st}(G_s[S])$. Therefore, to find a minimum st -separator T in $G_s[S]$ that is distinct from $S = N_{G_s[S]}(t)$, we apply the result of Corollary 5.2 by calling algorithm `OptimalMinSepByLbl` with parameters $G_s[S]$, and $\mathbf{1b1} = \mathbf{t}$ (line 22), and push the triple $\langle G_s[S], T, \mathbf{t} \rangle$ to the queue Q . If the minimal st -separator S is associated with the label \mathbf{s} or \mathbf{st} , then we need to find a minimum st -separator T in $G_s[S]$ that is distinct from both $S = N_{G_s[S]}(t)$, and $N_{G_s[S]}(s)$. Hence, in this case, algorithm `OptimalMinSepByLbl` is called with parameters $G_s[S]$, and $\mathbf{1b1} = \mathbf{st}$ (line 18). The symmetric case for finding a minimum st -separator in $G_t[S]$ that is distinct from S is outlined in lines 23-29.

The loop in lines 31-36 generates the graphs containing all minimal st -separators that cross S . That is, this loop implements the result of Theorem 4.2. Specifically, the algorithm generates the sets of graphs in $\mathcal{G}_1(u_i, v_i)$, and $\mathcal{G}_2(u_i, v_i)$ (see (9)), for every $i \in \{1, \dots, k\}$. For every graph $H \in \mathcal{G}_1(u_i, v_i)$ ($\mathcal{G}_2(u_i, v_i)$), it generates the graph H^{i-1} by adding to H the edges $\{(u_1, v_1), \dots, (u_{i-1}, v_{i-1})\}$ (see Theorem 4.2), finds a minimum-weight st -separator in H^{i-1} (line 35), and pushes it into the queue (line 36). By Theorem 4.2, it holds that $\mathcal{S}_{st}(H^{i-1}) \subseteq \{T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G) : T \nparallel S\}$. By Lemma B.1, neither J_s (the minimal st -separator closest to s), nor J_t are minimal st -separators in H^{i-1} . Hence, the label in line 36 is set to $_$.

Proposition B.1. Let G be a graph, $s, t \in V(G)$ two distinguished vertices, and ℓ be the maximal branch-depth among all induced paths in G having an endpoint in $\{s, t\}$. There exists an algorithm that lists the minimal st -separators of G in ascending order of their weight with delay $O(3^{\frac{4\ell}{3}} T(n, m) n^2 K^2)$, where $|V(G)| = n$, $|E(G)| = m$, K is the size of the largest minimal st -separator returned by the algorithm, and $T(n, m)$ is the runtime of an algorithm finding a minimum-weight st -separator.

Proof. Any standard implementation of sorted queue will enable extracting the minimum element and pushing an element into the queue in time $O(\log |Q|)$. Since $|Q| \leq 2^n$, then all queue operations on Q , B , and C , will take time $O(n)$. Constructing the graphs $G_s[S]$ and $G_t[S]$ in line 15 involves identifying the connected components $C_s(G, S)$ and $C_t(G, S)$, and takes time $O(n + m)$. In the worst case, the label associated with S is \mathbf{st} . Therefore, by Proposition C.1, the call to `OptimalMinSepByLbl` will take time $O(K^2 T(n, m))$, and this is done at most twice: once for graph $G_s[S]$, and once for graph $G_t[S]$.

The size of $\mathcal{M}(S)$ in line 30 is at most K^2 . Therefore, the loop in lines 33-36 is executed at most $2K^2$ times. Each such iteration generates all the graphs in \mathcal{G}_p (for $p \in \{1, 2\}$). By Lemma 2.2,

it holds that $|\mathcal{G}_p(u_i, v_i)| \leq 3^{\frac{2\ell}{3}}$. Hence, the loop in lines 33-36 will take time $O(3^{\frac{2\ell}{3}}T(n, m)n)$. In the worst case, $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(H^{i-1})$, for all $H \in \mathcal{G}_p(u_i, v_i)$. That is, the algorithm may output S at most $3^{\frac{2\ell}{3}}$ times. In this case, since $|\mathcal{S}_{st}(G)| \leq 2^n$, then by applying the buffering technique (Section 2.3), we can bound the delay by $O(3^{\frac{4\ell}{3}}T(n, m)n^2K^2)$. \square

Algorithm RankedEnumMinSep $s(G, \{s, t\})$

```

1:  $Q \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
2:  $B \leftarrow \emptyset$  {Data structure of distinct minimal  $st$ -separators
   that have not yet been printed, sorted by weight}
3:  $C \leftarrow \emptyset$  {Data structure of distinct elements that have
   been printed}
4: Num_Gen  $\leftarrow 0$  {tracks the number of minimal-seps gener-
   ated (including duplicates). See Section 2.3}
5: Let  $S \in \mathcal{L}_{st}(G)$  be a minimum  $st$ -separator of  $G$ 
6:  $Q.\text{push}(\langle G, S, - \rangle)$  { $Q$  is sorted by  $w(S)$ }
7: while  $Q \neq \emptyset$  do
8:    $\langle G, S, \text{lbl} \rangle \leftarrow Q.\text{pop}()$ 
9:   if  $S \notin B \cup C$  then
10:     $B \leftarrow B \cup \{S\}$ 
11:    if (Num_Gen mod  $(f(\ell) + 1) = 0$ ) then
12:       $S \leftarrow B.\text{pop}()$  {Recall:  $f(\ell) = 3^{\frac{4\ell}{3}}$ }
13:       $C \leftarrow C \cup \{S\}$ 
14:      print  $S$ 
15:    Construct the set  $\mathcal{G}_S = \{G_s[S], G_t[S]\}$  {Definition 5.1}

16:    if  $(s, t) \notin E(G_s[S])$  then
17:      if  $\text{lbl} \in \{s, \text{st}\}$  then
18:         $T \leftarrow \text{OptimalMinSepByLbl}(G_s[S], \{s, t\}, \text{st})$ 
19:         $Q.\text{push}(\langle G_s[S], T, \text{st} \rangle)$ 
20:      else
21:         $T \leftarrow \text{OptimalMinSepByLbl}(G_s[S], \{s, t\}, t)$ 
22:         $Q.\text{push}(\langle G_s[S], T, t \rangle)$ 
23:      if  $(s, t) \notin E(G_t[S])$  then
24:        if  $\text{lbl} \in \{t, \text{st}\}$  then
25:           $T \leftarrow \text{OptimalMinSepByLbl}(G_t[S], \{s, t\}, \text{st})$ 
26:           $Q.\text{push}(\langle G_t[S], T, \text{st} \rangle)$ 
27:        else
28:           $T \leftarrow \text{OptimalMinSepByLbl}(G_t[S], \{s, t\}, s)$ 
29:           $Q.\text{push}(\langle G_t[S], T, s \rangle)$ 
30:    Let  $\mathcal{M}(S) = \{(u_1, v_1), \dots, (u_k, v_k)\}$  be an ordered set
   of the non-edges of  $G[S]$ .
31:    for all  $p \in \{1, 2\}$  do
32:      for all  $i \in \{1, \dots, k\}$  do
33:        for all  $H \in \mathcal{G}_p(u_i, v_i)$  do
34:          Define  $H^{i-1}$  where  $E(H^{i-1}) = E(H) \cup$ 
            $\{(u_1, v_1), \dots, (u_{i-1}, v_{i-1})\}$ 
35:          Find  $T_p \in \mathcal{L}_{st}(H^{i-1})$ 
36:           $Q.\text{push}(\langle H^{i-1}, T_p, - \rangle)$ 
37:    Output the remaining separators in  $B$ 

```

Figure 2: Algorithm for enumerating $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$ in ranked order

C Missing Proofs

LEMMA 2.4. *Let A and B be two disjoint, non-adjacent subsets of $V(G)$. Let G' denote the graph that results by merging A and B into vertices a and b respectively. If $G[A]$ and $G[B]$ are connected, then $\mathcal{S}_{AB}(G) = \mathcal{S}_{ab}(G')$.*

Proof. Let $S \in \mathcal{S}_{AB}(G)$, with full components $C_A(G, S)$ and $C_B(G, S)$ containing A and B respectively. Let $D_a \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (C_A(G, S) \setminus A) \cup \{a\}$ and $D_b \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} (C_B(G, S) \setminus B) \cup \{b\}$. Since $G[C_A(G, S)]$ and $G[C_B(G, S)]$ are connected, then by the definition of merge, we have that $G'[D_a]$ and $G'[D_b]$ are connected as well. Since S separates $C_A(G, S)$ from $C_B(G, S)$, then S separates D_a from D_b . Since every edge from A to $v \in V(G) \setminus A$ is replaced by an edge from a to v , then D_a and D_b are full components of S in $\mathcal{C}_{G'}(S)$. Therefore, by Lemma 2.1, $S \in \mathcal{S}_{ab}(G')$.

Now, let $S \in \mathcal{S}_{ab}(G')$, with full components $C_a(G', S)$ and $C_b(G', S)$ containing a and b respectively. Since $N_{G'}(a) \subseteq S \cup C_a(G', S)$, and $N_{G'}(b) \subseteq S \cup C_b(G', S)$, then by the definition of merge, $N_G(A) \subseteq S \cup C_a(G', S)$, and $N_G(B) \subseteq S \cup C_b(G', S)$. Therefore, no connected component $C \in \mathcal{C}_G(S)$ contains vertices from both A and B . Since $G[A]$ is connected, $G'[C_a(G', S)]$ is connected, and $S \cap A = \emptyset$, then by the definition of merge, we have that $G'[(C_a(G', S) \setminus \{a\}) \cup A]$ is connected, and likewise that $G'[(C_b(G', S) \setminus \{b\}) \cup B]$ is connected. Since every edge from a to $v \in V(G) \setminus A$, is replaced by an edge from a vertex in A to v , then $(C_a(G', S) \setminus \{a\}) \cup A$ and $(C_b(G', S) \setminus \{b\}) \cup B$ are full components of S in $\mathcal{C}_G(S)$. Therefore, by Lemma 2.1, $S \in \mathcal{S}_{AB}(G)$. \square

LEMMA 4.5. *Let $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$ and let $\{(u_1, v_1), \dots, (u_k, v_k)\}$ be a set of non-edges of $G[S]$. Let G' be the graph where $V(G') = V(G)$ and $E(G') = E(G) \cup \bigcup_{i=1}^k (u_i, v_i)$. Then:*

$$\mathcal{S}_{st}(G') = \bigcap_{i=1}^k (\mathcal{S}_3^G(u_i, v_i) \cup \mathcal{S}_4^G(u_i, v_i)) \quad (23)$$

Proof. We first prove that $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G') \subseteq \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$ by induction on k . For $k = 1$, the claim follows immediately from Lemma 4.4. Assume the claim holds for $\ell \leq k - 1$, and we prove for $\ell = k$.

Consider the graph G'' where $V(G'') = V(G)$ and $E(G'') = E(G) \cup \bigcup_{i=1}^{k-1} (u_i, v_i)$. We claim that $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G'')$. Since every edge in $E(G'') \setminus E(G)$ is between a pair of vertices in S , then $C_s(G, S) = C_s(G'', S)$ and $C_t(G, S) = C_t(G'', S)$ remain separated in G'' . Since $C_s(G, S)$ and $C_t(G, S)$ are full connected components with respect to S in G , then $C_s(G'', S)$ and $C_t(G'', S)$ are full connected components with respect to S in G'' . By Lemma 2.1, $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G'')$. By the induction hypothesis, $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G'') \subseteq \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$. Now, since $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G'')$, and (u_k, v_k) is a non-edge in $G''[S]$, then by Lemma 4.4, it holds that $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G') \subseteq \mathcal{S}_{st}(G'') \subseteq \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$.

Now, let $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G')$. Suppose, by way of contradiction, that $T \notin \bigcap_{i=1}^k (\mathcal{S}_3(u_i, v_i) \cup \mathcal{S}_4(u_i, v_i))$. Let $i \in [1, k]$ such that $T \notin (\mathcal{S}_3(u_i, v_i) \cup \mathcal{S}_4(u_i, v_i))$. Since $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G') \subseteq \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$, then $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$. By Proposition 3.1, it holds that $T \in \mathcal{S}_1(u_i, v_i) \cup \mathcal{S}_2(u_i, v_i)$. But since $(u_i, v_i) \in E(G')$, it means that T does not separate s from t in G' . But then, $T \notin \mathcal{S}_{st}(G')$, a contradiction. Therefore, $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G') \subseteq \bigcap_{i=1}^k (\mathcal{S}_3(u_i, v_i) \cup \mathcal{S}_4(u_i, v_i))$.

Let $T \in \bigcap_{i=1}^k (\mathcal{S}_3(u_i, v_i) \cup \mathcal{S}_4(u_i, v_i))$, and let $C_s(G, T)$ and $C_t(G, T)$ denote the full connected components containing s and t , respectively. By assumption, for all (u_i, v_i) , it holds that $T \in \mathcal{S}_3(u_i, v_i) \cup \mathcal{S}_4(u_i, v_i)$. If $T \in \mathcal{S}_3(u_i, v_i)$, then u_i and v_i reside in the same connected component, and hence T separates s from t in the graph that results from adding the edge (u_i, v_i) . If $T \in \mathcal{S}_4(u_i, v_i)$, then the edge added between u_i and v_i cannot be between nodes in $C_s(G, T)$ and $C_t(G, T)$. Hence, in this case as well, T separates s from t in the graph that results from adding the edge (u_i, v_i) .

Overall, we have that T separates s from t in G' as well. If $T \notin \mathcal{S}_{st}(G')$, then there is an st -separator T' in G' where $T' \subset T$. Since $\mathbf{E}(G) \subseteq \mathbf{E}(G')$, then T' separates s from t in G . But then, $T \notin \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$, and we arrive at a contradiction. This completes the proof. \square

LEMMA 5.1. *Let $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$, and let G' denote the graph where $G[S]$ has been saturated to a clique. Then the following holds:*

$$\mathcal{S}_{st}(G') = \{T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G) : T \text{ is parallel to } S\} \quad (24)$$

Proof. Let $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G')$. By item 4 of Theorem 5.1, we have that $T \in \mathcal{S}(G)$, and by items 5 and 6, that the induced graphs $G[\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus T]$ and $G'[\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus T]$ have the same set of connected, and full connected components of T . Therefore, since $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G')$, and s and t reside in distinct full connected components in $G'[\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus T]$, then by Lemma 2.1, $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$. Since S is a clique in G' then by item 1 of Theorem 5.1, S is parallel to every minimal separator of G' . In particular, S and T are parallel in G' . By item 7 of Theorem 5.1, we have that S and T are parallel minimal separators in G as well. Hence, $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$ and T is parallel to S as required.

Now, let $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G)$ such that S and T are parallel in G . Let $C_s(G, T)$ and $C_t(G, T)$ denote the connected components of $G[\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus T]$ that contain s and t respectively. We show that $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G')$. Suppose, by way of contradiction, that $C_s(G, T)$ and $C_t(G, T)$ are connected in $G'[\mathbf{V}(G') \setminus T]$. Since every edge in $\mathbf{E}(G') \setminus \mathbf{E}(G)$ is between two vertices in S , then it must hold that $S \cap C_s(G, T) \neq \emptyset$ and $S \cap C_t(G, T) \neq \emptyset$. But this means that S and T are crossing in G , which is a contradiction. Hence, T separates s and t in G' . Since $\mathbf{E}(G) \subseteq \mathbf{E}(G')$, then $C_s(G, T)$ and $C_t(G, T)$ remain full components of T in G' . Hence, by Lemma 2.1, $T \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G')$. \square

Proposition C.1. For a graph G where $|\mathbf{V}(G)| = n$, and $|\mathbf{E}(G)| = m$, Algorithm 3 runs in time $T(n, m)$ if $\mathbf{1b1} = _$, $O(nT(n, m))$ if $\mathbf{1b1} \in \{\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{t}\}$, in time $O(n^2T(n, m))$ if $\mathbf{1b1} = \mathbf{st}$.

Proof. If $\mathbf{1b1} = _$, then the problem is that of finding the minimum-weight st -vertex-separator of G . By Theorem 2.1 this takes time $O(T(n, m))$.

If $\mathbf{1b1} \in \{\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{t}\}$, then by Corollary 5.2, we need to find the minimum st -separator in $|N_G(s)|$ ($|N_G(t)|$) graphs. Since $|N_G(s)| \leq n$, this will take time $O(nT(n, m))$. Finally, if $\mathbf{1b1} = \mathbf{st}$, then for every pair $\langle u, v \rangle \in N_G(s) \times N_G(t)$, we need to find the minimum st -separator in the graph H_{uv} , that results from merging edges (s, u) and (t, v) . By the above, this will take time $O(n^2T(n, m))$. \square

Algorithm OptimalMinSepByLbl($G, \{s, t\}, \text{lbl} \in \{\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{t}, \mathbf{st}, _ \}$)

```

1: if lbl = _ then
2:   return minimum  $st$ -separator of  $G$ 
3:  $S^{\text{OPT}} \leftarrow \perp, \text{OPT} \leftarrow \infty$ 
4: if lbl  $\in \{\mathbf{s}, \mathbf{t}\}$  then
5:    $a \leftarrow \text{lbl}$ 
6:   for all  $v \in N_G(a)$  do
7:     if  $(s, t) \notin \mathbf{E}(G^{(va)})$  then
8:        $S \leftarrow$  minimum  $st$ -separator in  $G^{(va)}$ 
9:       if  $|S| < \text{OPT}$  then
10:         $S^{\text{OPT}} \leftarrow S, \text{OPT} \leftarrow |S|$ 
11: else
12:   for all  $\langle u, v \rangle \in N_G(s) \times N_G(t)$  do
13:      $H_{uv} \leftarrow$  graph that results from merging  $(s, u)$  and
14:        $(t, v)$ 
15:     if  $(s, t) \notin \mathbf{E}(H_{uv})$  then
16:        $S \leftarrow$  minimum  $st$ -separator in  $H_{uv}$ 
17:       if  $|S| < \text{OPT}$  then
18:         $S^{\text{OPT}} \leftarrow S, \text{OPT} \leftarrow |S|$ 

```

Figure 3: Find optimal st -separator distinct from $N_G(s)$, $N_G(t)$, or both

D Enumeration Algorithms for st -Separators

In this section, we develop an enumeration algorithm that returns all (not necessarily minimal) st -separators of G in ranked order by cardinality or weight, and an enumeration algorithm that returns only the minimum-cardinality st -separators of G (i.e., $\mathcal{L}_{st}(G)$). We make the assumption that for all $v \in V$, $w(v) > 0$. We characterize vertices included in minimum-cardinality st -separators in Section D.1, and vertices excluded from any minimal st -separator (and hence, any minimum st -separator) in Section D.2. The resulting simple algorithms are then presented in Section D.3.

D.1 Characterizations of Vertices Included In Minimum st -Separators

In this section, we show that there is a polynomial-time algorithm, that given a subset of vertices $I \subseteq V(G)$, returns a minimum st -separator that contains I , if one exists.

Theorem D.1. (Menger [14]) Let G be an undirected graph and $s, t \in V(G)$. Then the minimum number of vertices separating s from t in G is equal to the maximum number of internally vertex-disjoint st -paths in G .

For brevity, we denote by $G-v$ the graph $G[V(G) \setminus \{v\}]$ induced by $V(G) \setminus \{v\}$, and by $\kappa(G)$ the connectivity of G .

Lemma D.1. Let $v \in V(G)$. There exists a minimum st -separator $S \in \mathcal{L}_{st}(G)$ that contains v if and only if $\kappa(G-v) = \kappa(G) - 1$.

Proof. Let $\kappa(G) = k$. Let $S \in \mathcal{L}_{st}(G)$ be such that $v \in S$. By Theorem D.1, there exist $|S| = k$ st -paths P_1, \dots, P_k that are internally disjoint. We claim that for every $i \in \{1, \dots, k\}$ it holds that $|V(P_i) \cap S| = 1$. If $|V(P_i) \cap S| = 0$ then $V(P_i) \cap S = \emptyset$, which means that $V(P_i) \subseteq V(G) \setminus S$, and hence s and t are connected in $G[V(G) \setminus S]$, which is a contradiction. If there is some $i \in \{1, \dots, k\}$, such that $|V(P_i) \cap S| \geq 2$, then since $V(P_j) \cap S \neq \emptyset$ for all $j \in \{1, \dots, k\}$, and since the st -paths are internally disjoint, then we have that $k - 1$ st -paths must meet at most $k - 2$ vertices. By the pigeon-hole principle, some pair of paths must share a vertex, and this is a contradiction to their disjointness. Therefore, v meets exactly one of the $|S| = k$ internally disjoint paths P_1, \dots, P_k . Consequently, the graph $G-v$ contains $|S| - 1 = k - 1$ internally disjoint st -paths, and by Menger's Theorem, $\kappa(G-v) = |S| - 1 = k - 1$.

Now suppose that $\kappa(G) = k$ and $\kappa(G-v) = k - 1$. By Menger's Theorem, $G-v$ has an st -separator S of size $k - 1$ that meets $k - 1$ pairwise disjoint st -paths P_1, \dots, P_{k-1} . Clearly, each of these $k - 1$ st -paths is also included in G . Since $\kappa(G) = \kappa(G-v) + 1$, there is an st -path P' in $G[V(G) \setminus S]$. Since $V(P') \subseteq V(G) \setminus S$ but $V(P') \not\subseteq V(G) \setminus (S \cup \{v\})$, or $V(P') \not\subseteq V(G-v) \setminus S$, we conclude that $v \in V(P')$, and this is the case for every st -path P' in $G[V(G) \setminus S]$. Hence, $S \cup \{v\}$ is an st -separator in G . Further, since $|S \cup \{v\}| = k = \kappa(G)$, then $S \cup \{v\}$ is a minimum st -separator in G that contains v . \square

Corollary D.1. Let $I \subseteq V(G)$, and let $k_I = |I|$. There exists a minimum separator $S \in \mathcal{L}_{st}(G)$ that contains I if and only if $\kappa(G[V(G) \setminus I]) = \kappa(G) - k_I$.

Proof. Let $\kappa(G) = k$. We prove by induction on k_I , the size of I . The case where $I = \emptyset$ is trivial, and the case where $|I| = 1$ is proved in Lemma D.1. So assume the claim holds for all sets I where $0 \leq |I| \leq \ell$, and we prove for the case where $|I| = \ell + 1$.

Let $x \in I$. By Lemma D.1, there exists a minimum separator $S \in \mathcal{L}_{st}(G)$ that contains x if and only if $\kappa(G - x) = \kappa(G) - 1$. Therefore, if $\kappa(G - x) > \kappa(G) - 1$, there does not exist a minimum separator that includes x , and hence, there does not exist one that contains I . Otherwise, let

$H \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} G-x$, and hence $\kappa(H) = k - 1$. Let $Y \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} I \setminus \{x\}$. Since $|Y| \leq \ell$ then we can apply the induction hypothesis. There is a minimum separator $S \in \mathcal{L}_{st}(H)$ that contains Y if and only if $\kappa(H[\mathbf{V}(H) \setminus Y]) = \kappa(H) - |Y| = \kappa(H) - \ell$. Since $H = G[\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus \{x\}]$, we get that

$$\begin{aligned} \kappa(G[\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus I]) &= \kappa(G[\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus (Y \cup \{x\})]) \\ &= \kappa(H[\mathbf{V}(H) \setminus Y]) = \kappa(H) - |Y| = \kappa(H) - \ell \\ &= \kappa(G) - 1 - \ell = \kappa(G) - (\ell + 1) \end{aligned}$$

□

Proposition D.1. Let $I \subseteq \mathbf{V}(G)$. We can determine whether there is a minimum st -separator $S \in \mathcal{L}_{st}(G)$ that contains I , and return one if exists, in time $O(n^{\frac{1}{2}}m)$.

Proof. The algorithm of Even and Tarjan [16] computes the connectivity of G , or $\kappa(G)$, in time $O(n^{\frac{1}{2}}m)$ by using network flow techniques. It also allows for constructing the $\kappa(G)$ internally disjoint st -paths, and hence returning a minimum separator (see also [8]).

It takes time $O(n + m)$ to construct the induced graph $G[\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus I]$, and again $O(n^{\frac{1}{2}}m)$ time to compute $\kappa(G[\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus I])$. By Corollary D.1, the answer is positive if and only if $\kappa(G) - |I| = \kappa(G[\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus I])$. Hence, the total time is $O(n^{\frac{1}{2}}m)$. □

D.2 Excluding Vertices from Minimal Separators

In this section, we characterize minimal st -separators that exclude a subset $U \subseteq \mathbf{V}(G)$ of vertices. We define some required notation. Let $U \subseteq \mathbf{V}(G)$. We denote by $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G, \bar{U})$ the set of minimal st -separators that exclude U . Formally:

$$\mathcal{S}_{st}(G, \bar{U}) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G) : S \subseteq \mathbf{V}(G) \setminus U\} \quad (25)$$

For a single vertex $u \in \mathbf{V}(G)$, we denote by $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G, \bar{u}) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G) : u \notin S\}$. We denote by $\kappa_{st}(G, \bar{U})$ the minimum size of any minimal st -separator that excludes U . Formally:

$$\kappa_{st}(G, \bar{U}) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \min \{|S| : S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G, \bar{U})\} \quad (26)$$

We denote by $\mathcal{L}_{st}(G, \bar{U})$ the subset of $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G, \bar{U})$ that have the smallest cardinality. Formally:

$$\mathcal{L}_{st}(G, \bar{U}) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \{S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G, \bar{U}) : |S| = \kappa_{st}(G, \bar{U})\} \quad (27)$$

Let $u \in \mathbf{V}(G)$; we denote by $\text{Sat}(G, u)$ the graph that results by adding edges between all vertices in $N_G[u]$. In other words, $\text{Sat}(G, u)$ is the graph where the set $N_G[u]$ has been *saturated*, and forms a clique. For a set of vertices $U \subseteq \mathbf{V}(G)$, we denote by $\text{Sat}(G, U)$ the graph that results by adding edges between all vertices in $N_G[u]$ for all $u \in U$. Formally, $\mathbf{V}(\text{Sat}(G, U)) = \mathbf{V}(G)$ and

$$\mathbf{E}(\text{Sat}(G, U)) \stackrel{\text{def}}{=} \mathbf{E}(G) \cup \bigcup_{u \in U} \{(x, y) : x, y \in N_G[u]\} \quad (28)$$

We prove that $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G, \bar{U}) = \mathcal{S}_{st}(\text{Sat}(G, U))$. We proceed by a series of lemmas.

Lemma D.2. Let $u \in \mathbf{V}(G)$ such that $N_G[u]$ forms a clique. Then $u \notin S$ for any minimal st -separator S of G .

Proof. Let S be a minimal st -separator of G . By Lemma 2.1, $G[\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus S]$ contains two full components $C_s(G, S)$ and $C_t(G, S)$ containing s and t respectively, such that $S = N_G(C_s(G, S)) = N_G(C_t(G, S))$. Therefore, if $u \in S$, then it has two neighbors $v_1 \in C_s(G, S)$ and $v_2 \in C_t(G, S)$ that are connected by an edge (because $N_G[u]$ is a clique). But then, there is an st -path in $G[\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus S]$ that avoids S , which contradicts the fact that S is an st -separator. \square

Lemma D.3. For every $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G, \bar{u})$, there exists a connected component $C_u \in \mathcal{C}_G(S)$ such that $N_G[u] \subseteq C_u \cup S$.

Proof. Let $C_u \in \mathcal{C}_G(S)$ be the connected component that contains u . Such a component must exist because $u \notin S$. If $N_G(u) \not\subseteq C_u \cup S$, then there exists a vertex $v \in N_G(u)$ that resides in a connected component $C_v \in \mathcal{C}_G(S)$ distinct from C_u . But this is a contradiction because, by definition, $(u, v) \in \mathbf{E}(G)$. Hence, $C_v = C_u$, and this proves the claim. \square

Lemma D.4. Let $u \in \mathbf{V}(G)$. Then $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G, \bar{u}) = \mathcal{S}_{st}(\text{Sat}(G, \{u\}))$.

Proof. Let $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G, \bar{u})$. Let $C_u \in \mathcal{C}_G(S)$ denote the connected component containing u in $G[\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus S]$. By Lemma D.3, $N_G[u] \subseteq C_u \cup S$. Therefore, no added edge in $\mathbf{E}(\text{Sat}(G, \{u\})) \setminus \mathbf{E}(G)$ connects vertices in distinct connected components in $\mathcal{C}_G(S)$. Hence, S separates s and t also in $\text{Sat}(G, \{u\})$. Since the addition of edges cannot eliminate any path between s and t , we get that S is a minimal st -separator also in $\text{Sat}(G, \{u\})$.

Now, let $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(\text{Sat}(G, \{u\}))$. Hence, $N_G[u]$ is a clique in $\text{Sat}(G, \{u\})$. By Lemma D.2, $u \notin S$. Since G is a subgraph of $\text{Sat}(G, \{u\})$, then if S separates s from t in $\text{Sat}(G, \{u\})$, it must separate s from t in G . Hence, S is an st -separator in G where $u \notin S$. It is left to show that S is a *minimal* st -separator in G . To that end, we show that the connected components $C_s, C_t \in \mathcal{C}_{\text{Sat}(G, \{u\})}(S)$, containing s and t respectively, are full connected components of S also in G . That is, we show that $S = N_G(C_s) = N_G(C_t)$. By Lemma 2.1, this proves that $S \in \mathcal{S}_{st}(G, \bar{u})$.

Denote by $D_s, D_t \in \mathcal{C}_G(S)$ the connected components containing s and t respectively in $G[\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus S]$. Since $G[D_s]$ ($G[D_t]$) is connected, $D_s \cap S = \emptyset$ ($D_t \cap S = \emptyset$), and $s \in D_s$ ($t \in D_t$), then $D_s \subseteq C_s$ ($D_t \subseteq C_t$). We now prove that $C_s \subseteq D_s$. We first consider the case where $u \notin C_s$. Hence, by definition of connected component of $G[\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus S]$, we have that $N_G[u] \cap C_s = \emptyset$. Since the only added edges are between vertices in $N_G(u)$, then $\mathbf{E}(\text{Sat}(G, u)[C_s]) = \mathbf{E}(G[C_s])$. Therefore C_s is a connected component containing s also in $G[\mathbf{V}(G) \setminus S]$. Also, since $N_G[u] \cap C_s = \emptyset$, then $N_G(C_s) = N_{\text{Sat}(G, \{u\})}(C_s) = S$ as required.

We now consider the case where $u \in C_s$, and suppose, by way of contradiction, that $C_s \not\subseteq D_s$. Let $v \in C_s \setminus D_s$. This means that there is a path from s to v in $\text{Sat}(G, \{u\})$ that avoids S . Let P denote the shortest such path. Then P passes through a single edge $(y, w) \in \mathbf{E}(\text{Sat}(G, u)) \setminus \mathbf{E}(G)$. In other words, there is a path P_{vy} from v to y in G that avoids S , and a path P_{sw} from s to w in G that avoids S . In particular, $\mathbf{V}(P_{sw}) \subseteq D_s$. By construction, $\{y, w\} \subseteq N_G(u)$. Since $\mathbf{V}(P_{ws}) \cap S = \emptyset$, $w \in N_G(u)$, and $\{u, w, y\} \cap S = \emptyset$, this means that $\{u, w, y\} \subseteq D_s$. But this means that the path $P_{vy}uP_{ws}$ is contained in G , and avoids S . Consequently, $v \in D_s$, and we arrive at a contradiction. Hence, $D_s = C_s$. Since $u \in C_s$, we get that $N_G(C_s) = N_{\text{Sat}(G, \{u\})}(C_s)$, making C_s a full connected component of S also in G . This completes the proof. \square

Theorem D.2. Let $U \subseteq \mathbf{V}(G)$. Then $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G, \bar{U}) = \mathcal{S}_{st}(\text{Sat}(G, U))$.

Proof. This follows from Lemma D.4 by a simple induction on $|U|$. \square

Corollary D.2. The following holds for every $U \subseteq \mathbf{V}(G)$. $\mathcal{L}_{st}(G, \bar{U}) = \mathcal{L}_{st}(\text{Sat}(G, U))$.

Proof. In Theorem D.2, we have shown that for any $U \subseteq \mathbf{v}(G)$, it holds that $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G, \bar{U}) = \mathcal{S}_{st}(\text{Sat}(G, U))$. Let $0 \leq k \leq n$ be an integer, and $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G, \bar{U})_k$ and $\mathcal{S}_{st}(\text{Sat}(G, U))_k$ denote the sets of minimal st -separators in $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G, \bar{U})$ and $\mathcal{S}_{st}(\text{Sat}(G, U))$ whose size is exactly k , respectively. Since $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G, \bar{U}) = \mathcal{S}_{st}(\text{Sat}(G, U))$, then $\mathcal{S}_{st}(G, \bar{U})_k = \mathcal{S}_{st}(\text{Sat}(G, U))_k$ for every integer $0 \leq k \leq n$. In particular, this is the case for $k = \kappa_{st}(G, \bar{U}) = \kappa_{st}(\text{Sat}(G, U))$. Hence, $\mathcal{L}_{st}(G, \bar{U}) = \mathcal{L}_{st}(\text{Sat}(G, U))$ (see (27)). \square

D.3 Ranked Enumeration Algorithms for all st -separators in Ranked Order, and an Enumeration Algorithm for Minimum st -separators

We directly apply the results of Sections D.1, and D.2 to the task of enumerating all st -separators in ranked order in Algorithm 4, and to the task of enumerating the minimum-cardinality st -separators $\mathcal{L}_{st}(G)$ in Algorithm 5. Both algorithms apply the standard Lawler technique with inclusion and exclusion constraints (see [19] for an overview), leading to simple polynomial-delay algorithms.

Algorithm RankedEnumSeps($G, \{s, t\}$)

```

1: Let  $S$  be a minimum-weight  $st$ -separator of  $G$ 
2:  $Q \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
3:  $Q.\text{push}(\langle G, S, I = \emptyset \rangle)$  { $Q$  is sorted by  $w(S)$ }
4: while  $Q \neq \emptyset$  do
5:    $\langle G, S, I \rangle \leftarrow Q.\text{pop}()$ 
6:   Print  $S$ 
7:   for all  $v_i \in S \setminus I = \{v_1, \dots, v_q\}$  do
8:      $I_i \leftarrow I \cup \{v_1, \dots, v_{i-1}\}$ 
9:      $H \leftarrow \text{Sat}(G, v_i)$  {Exclude  $v_i$ }
10:     $T \leftarrow$  minimum-weight  $st$ -separator in  $H[\mathbf{V}(H) \setminus I_i]$ 
11:     $Q.\text{push}(\langle H, T \cup I_i, I_i \rangle)$ 

```

Figure 4: Algorithm for enumerating all st -separators in ranked order

Algorithm MinimumSeps($G, \{s, t\}$)

```

1: Let  $S$  be a minimum-cardinality  $st$ -separator of  $G$ 
2:  $\kappa_G \leftarrow |S|$ 
3:  $Q \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
4:  $Q.\text{push}(\langle G, S, I = \emptyset \rangle)$ 
5: while  $Q \neq \emptyset$  do
6:    $\langle G, S, I \rangle \leftarrow Q.\text{pop}()$ 
7:   Print  $S$ 
8:   for all  $v_i \in S \setminus I = \{v_1, \dots, v_q\}$  do
9:      $I_i \leftarrow I \cup \{v_1, \dots, v_{i-1}\}$ 
10:     $H \leftarrow \text{Sat}(G, v_i)$  {Exclude  $v_i$  (see Lemma D.4)}
11:     $T \leftarrow$  minimum  $st$ -separator of  $H[\mathbf{V}(H) \setminus I_i]$ 
12:    if  $|T| = \kappa_G - |I_i|$  then
13:       $Q.\text{push}(\langle H, T, I_i \rangle)$  {See Corollary D.1}

```

Figure 5: Algorithm for enumerating minimum-cardinality st -separators

References

- [1] Stefan Arnborg, Derek G. Corneil, and Andrzej Proskurowski. Complexity of finding embeddings in a k -tree. *SIAM Journal on Algebraic Discrete Methods*, 8(2):277–284, 1987. [arXiv:https://doi.org/10.1137/0608024](https://doi.org/10.1137/0608024), doi:10.1137/0608024.
- [2] Anne Berry, Jean Paul Bordat, and Olivier Cogis. Generating all the minimal separators of a graph. *Int. J. Found. Comput. Sci.*, 11(3):397–403, 2000. doi:10.1142/S0129054100000211.
- [3] Anne Berry, Romain Pogorelnik, and Geneviève Simonet. An introduction to clique minimal separator decomposition. *Algorithms*, 3(2):197–215, 2010.
- [4] Daniel Bienstock. On the complexity of testing for odd holes and induced odd paths. *Discret. Math.*, 90(1):85–92, 1991. doi:10.1016/0012-365X(91)90098-M.
- [5] Hans L. Bodlaender and Fedor V. Fomin. Tree decompositions with small cost. *Discret. Appl. Math.*, 145(2):143–154, 2005.
- [6] Hans L. Bodlaender and Arie M. C. A. Koster. Combinatorial optimization on graphs of bounded treewidth. *Comput. J.*, 51(3):255–269, 2008.
- [7] Vincent Bouchitté and Ioan Todinca. Treewidth and minimum fill-in: Grouping the minimal separators. *SIAM J. Comput.*, 31(1):212–232, 2001. doi:10.1137/S0097539799359683.
- [8] Jianer Chen, Yang Liu, and Songjian Lu. An improved parameterized algorithm for the minimum node multiway cut problem. *Algorithmica*, 55(1):1–13, 2009. doi:10.1007/s00453-007-9130-6.
- [9] Jianer Chen, Yang Liu, Songjian Lu, Barry O’Sullivan, and Igor Razgon. A fixed-parameter algorithm for the directed feedback vertex set problem. *J. ACM*, 55(5):21:1–21:19, 2008.
- [10] Marek Cygan, Fedor V. Fomin, Lukasz Kowalik, Daniel Lokshtanov, Dániel Marx, Marcin Pilipczuk, Michal Pilipczuk, and Saket Saurabh. *Parameterized Algorithms*. Springer, 2015.
- [11] Rina Dechter. *Reasoning with Probabilistic and Deterministic Graphical Models: Exact Algorithms, Second Edition*. Synthesis Lectures on Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning. Morgan & Claypool Publishers, 2019.
- [12] Holger Dell, Christian Komusiewicz, Nimrod Talmon, and Mathias Weller. The PACE 2017 Parameterized Algorithms and Computational Experiments Challenge: The Second Iteration. In Daniel Lokshtanov and Naomi Nishimura, editors, *12th International Symposium on Parameterized and Exact Computation (IPEC 2017)*, volume 89 of *Leibniz International Proceedings in Informatics (LIPIcs)*, pages 30:1–30:12, Dagstuhl, Germany, 2018. Schloss Dagstuhl–Leibniz-Zentrum fuer Informatik. URL: <http://drops.dagstuhl.de/opus/volltexte/2018/8558>, doi:10.4230/LIPIcs.IPEC.2017.30.
- [13] Nicolas Derhy and Christophe Picouleau. Finding induced trees. *Discret. Appl. Math.*, 157(17):3552–3557, 2009. doi:10.1016/j.dam.2009.02.009.
- [14] Reinhard Diestel. *Graph Theory, 4th Edition*, volume 173 of *Graduate texts in mathematics*. Springer, 2012.

- [15] Shimon Even and Guy Even. *Graph Algorithms, Second Edition*. Cambridge University Press, 2012.
- [16] Shimon Even and Robert Endre Tarjan. Network flow and testing graph connectivity. *SIAM J. Comput.*, 4(4):507–518, 1975. doi:10.1137/0204043.
- [17] Jörg Flum and Martin Grohe. *Parameterized Complexity Theory*. Texts in Theoretical Computer Science. An EATCS Series. Springer, 2006. doi:10.1007/3-540-29953-X.
- [18] Masanobu Furuse and Koichi Yamazaki. A revisit of the scheme for computing treewidth and minimum fill-in. *Theor. Comput. Sci.*, 531:66–76, 2014.
- [19] Konstantin Golenberg, Benny Kimelfeld, and Yehoshua Sagiv. Optimizing and parallelizing ranked enumeration. *Proc. VLDB Endow.*, 4(11):1028–1039, 2011.
- [20] Robert Haas and Michael Hoffmann. Chordless paths through three vertices. *Theor. Comput. Sci.*, 351(3):360–371, 2006. doi:10.1016/j.tcs.2005.10.021.
- [21] Horst W. Hamacher. An $o(k \cdot n^4)$ algorithm for finding the k best cuts in a network. *Oper. Res. Lett.*, 1(5):186–189, 1982.
- [22] Pinar Heggernes. Minimal triangulations of graphs: A survey. *Discrete Mathematics*, 306(3):297–317, 2006. Minimal Separation and Minimal Triangulation. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0012365X05006060>, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.disc.2005.12.003>.
- [23] Monika Rauch Henzinger, Satish Rao, and Harold N. Gabow. Computing vertex connectivity: New bounds from old techniques. *J. Algorithms*, 34(2):222–250, 2000.
- [24] Arkady Kanevsky. On the number of minimum size separating vertex sets in a graph and how to find all of them. In *SODA*, pages 411–421. SIAM, 1990.
- [25] Ken-ichi Kawarabayashi and Yusuke Kobayashi. The induced disjoint paths problem. In *IPCO*, volume 5035 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 47–61. Springer, 2008.
- [26] Ton Kloks and Dieter Kratsch. Listing all minimal separators of a graph. *SIAM J. Comput.*, 27(3):605–613, 1998. doi:10.1137/S009753979427087X.
- [27] Ton Kloks, Dieter Kratsch, and Jeremy P. Spinrad. On treewidth and minimum fill-in of asteroidal triple-free graphs. *Theor. Comput. Sci.*, 175(2):309–335, 1997.
- [28] Daphne Koller and Nir Friedman. *Probabilistic Graphical Models - Principles and Techniques*. MIT Press, 2009.
- [29] Tuukka Korhonen. Listing small minimal separators of a graph. *CoRR*, abs/2012.09153, 2020. URL: <https://arxiv.org/abs/2012.09153>, arXiv:2012.09153.
- [30] Tuukka Korhonen, Jeremias Berg, and Matti Järvisalo. Solving graph problems via potential maximal cliques: An experimental evaluation of the bouchitté-todincea algorithm. *ACM J. Exp. Algorithmics*, 24(1):1.9:1–1.9:19, 2019.

- [31] Kai-Yuan Lai, Hsueh-I Lu, and Mikkel Thorup. Three-in-a-tree in near linear time. In *Proceedings of the 52nd Annual ACM SIGACT Symposium on Theory of Computing, STOC 2020*, page 1279–1292, New York, NY, USA, 2020. Association for Computing Machinery. doi:10.1145/3357713.3384235.
- [32] Eugene L. Lawler. A procedure for computing the k best solutions to discrete optimization problems and its application to the shortest path problem. *Management Science*, 18(7):401–405, 1972. URL: <http://www.jstor.org/stable/2629357>.
- [33] Eugene L. Lawler, Jan Karel Lenstra, and A. H. G. Rinnooy Kan. Generating all maximal independent sets: Np-hardness and polynomial-time algorithms. *SIAM J. Comput.*, 9(3):558–565, 1980. doi:10.1137/0209042.
- [34] Chao Li and Maomi Ueno. An extended depth-first search algorithm for optimal triangulation of bayesian networks. *Int. J. Approx. Reason.*, 80:294–312, 2017.
- [35] Dániel Marx. Parameterized graph separation problems. *Theor. Comput. Sci.*, 351(3):394–406, 2006.
- [36] Hiroshi Nagamochi and Toshihide Ibaraki. *Algorithmic Aspects of Graph Connectivity*, volume 123 of *Encyclopedia of Mathematics and its Applications*. Cambridge University Press, 2008.
- [37] Andreas Parra and Petra Scheffler. Characterizations and algorithmic applications of chordal graph embeddings. *Discret. Appl. Math.*, 79(1-3):171–188, 1997. doi:10.1016/S0166-218X(97)00041-3.
- [38] Hong Shen and Weifa Liang. Efficient enumeration of all minimal separators in a graph. *Theoretical Computer Science*, 180(1):169–180, 1997. URL: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S0304397597838091>, doi:[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3975\(97\)83809-1](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0304-3975(97)83809-1).
- [39] Ken Takata. Space-optimal, backtracking algorithms to list the minimal vertex separators of a graph. *Discret. Appl. Math.*, 158(15):1660–1667, 2010. doi:10.1016/j.dam.2010.05.013.
- [40] Hisao Tamaki. Computing treewidth via exact and heuristic lists of minimal separators. In *SEA²*, volume 11544 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 219–236. Springer, 2019.
- [41] Yufei Tao and Ke Yi. Intersection joins under updates. *J. Comput. Syst. Sci.*, 124:41–64, 2022.
- [42] Jan Arne Telle and Yngve Villanger. Connecting terminals and 2-disjoint connected subgraphs. In *WG*, volume 8165 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 418–428. Springer, 2013.
- [43] Vijay V. Vazirani and Mihalis Yannakakis. Suboptimal cuts: Their enumeration, weight and number (extended abstract). In *ICALP*, volume 623 of *Lecture Notes in Computer Science*, pages 366–377. Springer, 1992.
- [44] Zijian Xu, Dejun Mao, and Vorapong Suppakitpaisarn. PACE Solver Description: Computing Exact Treedepth via Minimal Separators. In Yixin Cao and Marcin Pilipczuk, editors, *15th International Symposium on Parameterized and Exact Computation (IPEC 2020)*, volume 180 of *Leibniz International Proceedings in Informatics (LIPIcs)*, pages 31:1–31:4, Dagstuhl, Germany, 2020. Schloss Dagstuhl–Leibniz-Zentrum für Informatik. URL: <https://drops.dagstuhl.de/opus/volltexte/2020/13334>, doi:10.4230/LIPIcs.IPEC.2020.31.

- [45] Zijian Xu and Vorapong Suppakitpaisarn. On the size of minimal separators for treedepth decomposition. *CoRR*, abs/2008.09822, 2020.